
Reverse Engineering and Machine Learning for Concept Creation of a Data Mining Hardware

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ADP

Reverse Engineering and Machine Learning for concept creation of a data mining hardware

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Background

Within the research project ETHAN, the FSR is working on condition monitoring concepts and measurement aggregation hardware in the context of the digital twin for future (hybrid) electric flight systems. In coordination with several partners, the goal is to develop a condition monitoring concept from scratch. Sub-aspects are the definition of suitable algorithms, on-board measurement hardware and software infrastructure. The usage of machine learning methods will be a strong focus to derive system health states and predict Remaining Useful Lifetimes.

Task

The task in this project is to derive and define requirements for the measurement hardware of an onboard data logger. Even though a wide range of requirements is already defined with the industry partner RRE, several dependencies are not yet fully described. Possible dependencies are to be examined and identified using Machine Learning in a reverse engineering process: In a first step, a literature review will deliver suitable open source data sets (e.g. from a data challenge) or a generic simulation framework. The data is then to be manipulated to analyze the influences of data quality on modeling performance. Finally, requirements to the measurement and data logging hardware can be derived. The project closes with a comprehensive documentation and presentation of the results.

Subtasks

Within the scope of the project the following points are to be dealt with:

- Literature review on suitable data sets
- Design and implementation of appropriate methods for anomaly detection
- Manipulation of data (e.g. sampling frequency, resolution, transmission delay, ...)
- Evaluation of influences on diagnostic performance
- Definition of requirements, specification and concept development of measurement hardware
- Documentation and presentation of the results

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Erklärung zur Abschlussarbeit

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Abstract

In the context of monitoring data loggers, the first step is to diagnose the data characteristics and determine the label based on sensor measurements. Once the label dependencies are known, Machine Learning can be employed to learn data patterns and predict future data states to indicate the system's health. This combination of diagnosis and prognosis is known as Prognostic Health Management (PHM), which enhances system monitoring for on-board data loggers. However, this project focuses on reverse engineering, where the PHM environment and label dependencies are already provided. The aim is to investigate how corrupt data quality affects diagnostic performance and to determine the design requirements for onboard data logger measurement hardware in the ETHAN framework.

In this project, the flightpath data was generated using MATLAB Simulink, which converts DC (Direct Current) power to AC (Alternating Current) power using an ideal inverter to power an AC motor. The resistance input into the system is represented by the flightpath, which controls the AC motor using Ohm's Law. The recorded values of the motor serve as feedback for the system. The flightpath input is a linear piecewise function that includes three plateaus representing different stages of flight. Although the circuit to which the flightpath input is connected is ideal, there are errors in the generated values due to noise added to the input and outputs.

Data corruption can occur through reduced sampling frequency and data resolution, as well as the implementation of three different transmission delays. This investigation considers not only uncorrupted training, which involves training a machine learning model without any data corruption, but also corrupted training, which involves training a machine learning model with corrupted data in four different cases. Comparing the uncorrupted and corrupted training, it is evident that corrupted training results in worse performance, as a corrupted model lacks the necessary information to predict the full-frame data. Models that have been corrupted do not contain the essential information and are therefore unable to function correctly due to the deletion of crucial data.

The impact of the three different transmission delays on data quality is ranked as $M3 > M1 > M2$. $M2$ has the least impact on data quality, as it neither adds extreme measurements to the data nor deletes any information, but merely switches the order of the rows due to the large size of the data (i.e., 10 million) and its repetitiveness (10 flightpaths). $M3$ has a significant impact on data quality, as it essentially deletes relevant information in the features. On the other hand, $M1$ is in the middle, as it deletes the repetitiveness. By comparing all methods used in this project, it can be concluded that the maximum tolerance for transmission delay is 0.625% of $1/3$ of the original data with all the methods implemented in this project under the discussed constraints. Interrupting the data entity by introducing errors or extreme values has a greater impact on diagnostics performance than making internal changes ($M2$, i.e., row switches). The use of F_s deletes data details, such as repetitiveness and rows, has minimal impact. Both $M2$ and reducing F_s interrupt the data sequence, but their impact is negligible ($M3 > M1 > M2 > F_s$). In general, the data sequence is the least important factor affecting diagnostics performance, provided that the data entity remains unchanged.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	ETHAN Project Background and Link to this Project	1
1.2	Aims of the Project	2
2	State of the Art	4
2.1	Maintenance Strategies before PHM	4
2.2	Current Usage of PHM	8
2.3	Possible Errors in Data Driven PHM	10
2.3.1	Impact of F_s and Resolution of Data Generation	10
2.3.2	Errors in Data Transmission and Storage	10
2.3.3	Error in ML	11
2.3.4	Risks of High-class imbalanced Data	12
2.4	Overview of Data Mining Algorithms	12
2.4.1	Fine Tree Model	13
2.4.2	Naive Bayes Model	13
2.4.3	Narrow Neural Network Model	14
2.4.4	k-Nearest Neighbors Model	14
2.4.5	Support Vector Machines Model	15
2.5	Evaluation Methods	15
3	Methodology	17
3.1	Concept of Operation of the Final Design	17
3.2	Defining the Scope of the Project	18
3.3	Determination of Data Mining Algorithms	18
3.4	Trade-off of Evaluation Methods	20
4	Final Design	21
4.1	Overview of the Final Design	21
4.2	Identification and Creation of a Dataset	23
4.2.1	Data Acquisition via Open Source data	23
4.2.2	MATLAB Overview and Workflow	25
4.2.3	MATLAB Scripts of generating Flightpath, Noise, Wind, and Randomness	26
4.2.4	Overview of Flightpath Circuit	33
4.3	Determination of Labelling	36
4.3.1	Truth Output generated from Flightpath	36
4.3.2	Manual Label Output by Specification of Measurement Restrictions	37
4.3.3	20% Corrupted Output based on Truth Output	39
4.3.4	5% Corrupted Output based on Truth Output	39

4.4	ML with Uncorrupted Training	41
4.5	Corruption of Data Quality by Induced Error	42
4.5.1	Reduce F_s	42
4.5.2	Implementation of Transmission Delay	42
4.6	ML with Corrupted Training	49
4.6.1	F_s at 2.5kHz	49
4.6.2	20s M1 Transmission Delay	49
4.6.3	F_s at 2.5kHz & 20s M1 Transmission Delay	50
4.6.4	F_s at 2.5kHz & 80s M3 Transmission Delay at AC Current only	50
5	Data Analysis of different Corruption Methods on Diagnostics Performance	51
5.1	ML with Uncorrupted Training	51
5.1.1	Reducing F_s on the Model trained by Uncorrupted Data	51
5.1.2	Implement Transmission Delay M1 on the Model trained by Uncorrupted Data	52
5.1.3	Implement Transmission Delay M2 on the Model trained by Uncorrupted Data	54
5.1.4	Implement Transmission Delay M3 on the Model trained by Uncorrupted Data	56
5.2	ML with Corrupted Training	57
5.2.1	Implement Transmission Delay M1 on the Model trained by Corrupted Data	57
5.2.2	Implement Transmission Delay M2 on the Model trained by Corrupted Data	60
5.2.3	Implement Transmission Delay M3 on the Model trained by Corrupted Data	62
6	Evaluation	66
6.1	Verification and Validation of Project Requirements	66
6.2	Overview of the Data Characteristics	66
6.3	Summary of Reducing F_s	69
6.4	Summary of M1	69
6.5	Summary of M2	69
6.6	Summary of M3	70
6.7	Summary of difference between Uncorrupted and Corrupted Training for M1	70
6.8	Conclusion	71
7	Further Improvement	73
7.1	Implementing Weighted Algorithm	73
7.2	Different Approach of Reducing Resolution	73
7.3	Frequency-Domain Analysis	73
Appendix		78
A	Plots/Figures/Tables Chapter 3	79
B	Plots/Figures/Tables Chapter 4	84
C	Plots/Figures/Tables Chapter 5	95

List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
PHM	Prognostic and Health Management
RUL	Remaining Useful Life
CPE	Critical Project Elements
DR	Design Requirement
FR	Functional Requirement
M1	Transmission Delay Method 1
M2	Transmission Delay Method 2
M3	Transmission Delay Method 3
AUC	Area Under Curve
FT	Fine Tree model
NB	Naive Bayes model
NNN	Narrow Neural Network
TD	Transmission Delay
DS	Down-sampling
ML	Machine Learning
%a.D	Percent (Shown) as Decimal
DC	Direct Current
AC	Alternating Current
CART	Classification and Regression Trees
NN	Neural Network
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
FFNN	Feed Forward Neural Network
kNN	K-Nearest Neighbours
SVM	Support Vector Machines
TP	True Positive
FP	False Positive
FN	False Negative
TN	True Negative
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristic
CONOPS	Concept of Operation
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
CM	Corrective Maintenance
PdM	Predictive Maintenance
CBM	Condition-Based Monitoring
ETHAN	Efficient Technology for High-power-density Aerospace Propulsion
NaN	Not a Number

List of Variables

Variables	Definition
F_s	Sampling Frequency
V_{res}	Voltage Resolution
λ	Wave Length
t	time
Noise	Noise used for input
q	Wind Curve Skew
S	Wind Scale
V	Voltage
I	Currefnt
LP	Number of Positive Waves
LN	Number of Negative Waves
σ	Standard Deviation

1 Introduction

Effective monitoring and prediction of system health is crucial in Industry 4.0, where interconnected systems are becoming increasingly prevalent. This is to avoid financial losses, safety hazards, high maintenance costs, and system failures. Predicting the health status of high-tech equipment is more efficient than waiting for failure, as these systems usually comprise several costly materials and components. Poor data quality can cause a company to lose 8-12% of its income[71][50].

There are two methods for system monitoring: diagnostic and prognostic approaches. The diagnostic approach detects system malfunctions by detecting states and assessing health, while the prognostic approach forecasts such occurrences by assessing health and generating advice based on that.

Prognostics and Health Management (PHM) is a revolutionary engineering methodology that enables continuous system health assessment while it is operating and provides the ability to predict its future state based on up-to-date information. PHM integrates multiple disciplines such as sensing technologies, physics of failure, ML, modern statistics, and reliability engineering. Using PHM helps engineers to transform health states and data into useful insights about the system, which can improve our understanding of the system and provide a plan to sustain its original intended function. Although initially developed for the aerospace industry, PHM is now being explored in various applications such as manufacturing, automotive, railway, energy, and heavy industry[41](Details see section 2.2).

PHM for electrical drive systems is used as a foundation for efficient maintenance operations during the design phase in Industry 4.0. The procedures follow the Open System Architecture for Condition-Based Maintenance (OSA-CBM). The OSA-CBM procedures comprise Data Acquisition (DA), Data Manipulation (DM), State Detection (SD), Health Assessment (HA), Prognostics Assessment (PA), Advisory Generation (AG), and Presentation.

PHM enables system health assessment under operating conditions and prediction of the remaining useful life (RUL) of systems. RUL is a critical parameter for predictive maintenance that estimates the remaining lifetime of a component before requiring replacement[39]. PHM facilitates a condition-based maintenance approach, where only damaged parts are repaired or replaced, resulting in significant reductions in the life cycle costs of the system[41]. This project aims to investigate how corrupted data quality affects diagnostic performance in such a system. By using reverse engineering PHM, it is possible to analyze the impact of corrupted data imputed into a prediction model, enabling the omission of redundant or excessive measurements and reducing inspection costs.

1.1 ETHAN Project Background and Link to this Project

This project was carried out as part of the Efficient Technology for High-power-density Aerospace Propulsion (ETHAN) project, which is a joint research project between Flight Systems and Automatic

Control (FSR), Rolls Royce Electrical (RRE), and other universities. As part of the project, FSR is responsible for creating a robust database that enables predictive maintenance for future electric aircraft. This involves designing an IT (Information Technology) architecture, measuring hardware, and conceptualizing PHM algorithms [72].

The primary goal of the ETHAN project is to gather accurate data for future predictive maintenance applications in the IT architecture. Therefore, analyzing error propagation in data is essential to identifying the correct data. The project aims to evaluate the effectiveness of various ML models and approaches when presented with error-prone data caused by malfunctions such as anomalies in the sampling frequency (F_s) and transmission delays.

To achieve this goal, the on-board data logger preprocesses, structures, compresses, and packages measurements and then sends them to the RRE central database. The FSR's off-board monitoring and data handling intelligent algorithm module receives the data for further analysis [72].

1.2 Aims of the Project

This project aims to investigate the impact of induced errors on the diagnostics performance and data quality of system monitoring. Specifically, it seeks to determine how much the input variables, such as F_s , voltage resolution (V_{res}), and data quality, can be reduced while still maintaining the required accuracy for system monitoring. The output of the system monitoring is either a healthy or faulty status.

When errors are induced in the dataset, it can affect the size of the data. For instance, decreasing the F_s will reduce the data size, while increasing it will expand it. A larger dataset has several advantages, such as it is easier to generate labels in ML, find patterns in data, and train a ML model. A larger dataset requires more precise sensor measurements and incurs higher maintenance costs, such as increased effort for data analysis. Additionally, when dealing with a larger dataset, there are several drawbacks to consider. These include increased training time, computational costs, and model complexity. These factors can impact the overall quality of the data, even when the dataset is large. As a result, it becomes more challenging to extract valuable information from the data due to the presence of misleading information.

However, a small dataset has some drawbacks. Firstly, it may be challenging to identify accurate correlations among the sensors, making it difficult to select or extract features as labels. Secondly, a larger dataset allows for easier examination of data patterns, such as the average, standard deviation, histograms, and normal distribution, which may not be apparent in smaller datasets. However, the usefulness of these data patterns depends on the dataset's size. Thirdly, a larger dataset may produce a more accurate model. Still, the predicted accuracy does not increase linearly with the size of the dataset.

The accuracy-data size tradeoff is comparable to an evolution saturation model, as depicted in figure 1.1. In the graph, MaxNumSplits represents the training sample size, and it shows that an accuracy of 90%+ can be maintained as long as the training sample size is approximately 6. At the beginning of the graph, the data size required for the desired accuracy of system monitoring is proportional. However, within a certain range of data size, the increase in accuracy is negligible.

Figure 1.1: The Trade-off between Training Sample Size and Model Accuracy [60]

Therefore, it is unnecessary to have a high data frequency to achieve the desired level of accuracy. Thus, reducing the dataset to the desired level is necessary to optimize costs. The primary goal of the research on "Reverse Engineering and ML for Concept Creation of a Data Mining Hardware" is to analyze how input data errors will affect the diagnostic performance, such as the PHM matrix. This analysis will enable the creation of a dataset that can still achieve the desired level of accuracy for system monitoring. The specifications for data quality can be utilized to determine the design requirements for the onboard data logger measurement hardware in the ETHAN framework.

2 State of the Art

In this chapter, the discussion covers strategies prior to PHM, the current usage of PHM, and the impact of errors in various aspects on data. Additionally, the five most common ML algorithms and evaluation methods are presented.

2.1 Maintenance Strategies before PHM

Maintenance management is a recurrent topic when discussing ML applications. This subject is strongly linked to the evolution of available technologies and industry needs. Despite the different classifications of maintenance found in literature, and even the conducted studies on existing classifications [24], this report provides a basic overview to contextualize the project.

Moubray presents a historical distinction of maintenance management within three main generations [53]. Complementing this division with the highlights given in the lecture ML Applications [58], when discussing the phenomenon of wear-out, a general classification can be deduced:

The first generation of maintenance management is linked to a corrective maintenance (CM) strategy. CM can be summarized as "repair after damage", meaning that this strategy relies on substituting a failed component with a new one. Generally, this approach is attributed to low cost, as it only requires basic maintenance resources [68]. A good example of its application could be the maintenance of general light bulbs, which are non-essential components with low impact in case of outage [76]. However, relying solely on this method can become an expensive investment, as the consequences of a component's failure could lead to several failure events and result in a major catastrophe.

The second generation refers to preventive maintenance (PM), which promotes a scheduled maintenance approach. This strategy is based on experience and different control methods over working systems, from which guidelines can be deduced, and periodic scheduled replacements of certain components can be planned based on cost, time, or failure [9]. Therefore, overhauls are conducted before the component fails. PM has a wide range of applications, from routine tasks such as cleaning and lubrication to more extensive maintenance such as reconditioning of certain parts. Different examples are regular checks on HVAC (Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning) and electric systems or validation of compliance with code standards [78]. However, using PM can lead to non-optimal usage of component lifetime. Since the replacement of a component is scheduled before its expected time to failure, it usually results in unnecessary repairs [52].

The third generation will be predictive maintenance (PdM) methods, which promote maintenance based on Condition-Based Monitoring (CBM). Using this method, maintenance of a component is conducted when predictions point to an impending minimum operational state, reducing "machine downtime, costs, control, and quality of production" [81]. As an example, PdM is widely used in the energy industry,

where data analytics can anticipate fluctuations in energy demand so that potential system failures can be avoided [32]. Figure 2.1 presents a representation of how the application of the mentioned maintenance techniques is conducted over the lifetime of a specific component.

Figure 2.1: Application of Maintenance Techniques over Component's Degradation Process[59]

Currently, all the maintenance approaches mentioned above are often implemented as a single maintenance management technique for a given system. CM is typically used for components or items that would not represent a high cost for replacement or have a low impact on the entire system if damaged. PM is a suitable approach when there is low variance in the event of component outage. If the behavior of a component in terms of outage is deterministic, then PM might provide a good result as a maintenance strategy, since scheduled replacements can be planned with a low failure rate. In contrast, methods based on CBM are more appropriate for applications where failure events cannot be well predicted, and continued monitoring of components is necessary to ensure proper maintenance timing. However, since CBM techniques might require significant logistics and infrastructure, components with a low impact risk may be better off being replaced through CM tasks. A comprehensive overview of the discussed areas of application can be found in Figure 2.2[57].

Figure 2.2: Cases of Application of Maintenance Techniques

The main focus of this project is on PdM. PdM involves analyzing historical data to prevent failures and avoid unnecessary replacements. A PdM program primarily detects early signs of faults or failures and initiates maintenance procedures at the right time [65]. This detection includes both diagnostics and prognostics, which involve detecting the type of malfunction and predicting its evolution.

ML is currently being emphasized as a tool to improve PdM. With the availability of new technologies, such as more accurate sensors, there is more data available for complex systems in the industrial environment. This creates an ideal environment for ML to build predictive programs that can detect hidden patterns within the data [15]. Figure 2.3, provided in the paper by Carvalho et al., sketches the process flow of how ML methods are implemented in PdM, divided into clear steps.

Figure 2.3: Design steps for ML model in PdM.[15]

In PdM, analysis of systems is conducted by using historical data to prevent reaching failure states while avoiding unnecessary replacements. Therefore, a PdM program primarily detects early signs of faults or failures and then initiates maintenance procedures at the right time [65]. This detection encompasses both diagnostics and prognostics, which describe the steps of detecting the type of malfunction and predicting its evolution.

Currently, special emphasis is placed on using ML as a tool to improve PdM. With the availability of new technologies, such as sensors, which supply more data for systems. This environment has a high potential for ML to build predictive programs that can detect hidden patterns within data of complex systems [15].

The historical data selection step deals with the acquisition of relevant data to build an ML model. Data preprocessing is the step in which data is transformed to make it more accessible in terms of computational resources. The model selection, model training, and model validation steps aim to identify a suitable ML model that satisfies a given purpose given the available data. The model maintenance step refers to setting a maintenance routine for the ML model, as the application environment might change over time.

The implementation of ML in PdM is defining new areas of application and specialized methodologies to empower PdM, such as the already discussed PHM and CBM approaches [4] [13]. To avoid confusion, it is essential to highlight the distinction between PdM, CBM, and PHM. CBM uses the data collected during the monitoring process of a specific component to ensure that the item is under the established working conditions and performs maintenance when the threshold of operational conditions is exceeded. PdM, on the other hand, uses data and measurements to assess the development of future degradation and failure of a component. Therefore, the overlap of CBM and PdM can be noticed in the way that PdM is using monitoring systems present in CBM from which predictive programs can be developed. Furthermore, PHM falls in the ground of PdM strategies, specifically PHM uses data obtained from condition monitoring to predict the future states of components and elaborate models for diagnostic and prognostic purposes [14]. Thus, PHM appears to be a key technology to enable optimal CBM strategies. To maintain the right trade-off between expenses designated to develop and integrate CBM techniques and safety in machinery, PHM approaches can determine the optimal timing for performing maintenance when needed [41].

In Figure 2.4, the distribution of costs associated with CM, PM, and CBM is explained. This chart clarifies the aim of defining the optimal area for implementing advanced maintenance techniques while accounting for the costs bound to their incorporation, such as infrastructure and logistic-derived expenses. For a low number of outages, a CM approach generally can be taken, and for a high volume of failures, PM is more adequate. Nevertheless, the ideal trade-off point can usually be achieved by means of CBM methods, as previously mentioned.

Figure 2.4: Costs Plot in Maintenance Management Techniques [41].

Finally, as discussed by Hashemian et al. [27], industry should tend to deploy PdM based methods to assess maintenance management, and to no longer assume a fix failure time for the components or items but also to be considerate of a random time of failure.

2.2 Current Usage of PHM

PHM is the science and technology of assessing the health of machinery, predicting when maintenance should be performed, and improving system reliability. CBM, on the other hand, is a maintenance strategy that uses the actual condition of equipment to decide when maintenance should be performed. In other words, PHM is concerned with predicting when maintenance is needed, while CBM is concerned with deciding when maintenance is actually performed.[30] PHM is a strategy which enables CBM.[41].

PHM is a technology that uses sensor data to monitor system health, detect anomalies, diagnose faults, and predict the RUL of a system throughout its lifetime. PHM is particularly useful for complex systems that generate massive amounts of real-time data from various resources. Advanced data processing tools are required to automatically relate the characteristics hidden within the incoming data.

To handle the proliferation of heterogeneous and multi-dimensional data streams, various ML methods have been used, such as support vector machines, random forest, principal component analysis, particle filtering, and hidden Markov model. In recent years, deep learning via deep neural networks has become more popular because it can automatically process highly non-linear and complex feature extraction from raw data.

Figure 2.5 illustrates the three-step process used in PHM, including data collection, artificial feature extraction, and health recognition. In the first step, sensors integrated within the system constantly collect different types of data such as vibration, acoustic emission, temperature, and current transformer data. In the second step, commonly-used features, such as time-domain, frequency-domain, and time–frequency-domain features, are extracted from the collected data. Feature selection methods, such as filters, wrappers, and embedded methods, are then used to select sensitive features of the health states of machines from the extracted features. In the third step, ML models are trained with labeled sample data to find relationships between features and the health state of the system.

Figure 2.5: Diagnosis Procedure of PHM using Traditional ML Theories. [48]

The current deployment of PHM strategies is found in multiple fields, including the Aerospace Industry, Wind Energy Industry, and Manufacturing.

In the Aerospace Industry, PHM is employed to predict the RUL of components and systems, enabling proactive maintenance and reducing the risk of unexpected failures. Airbus, for example, has implemented PHM technology on its A320 aircraft to monitor engine health and predict maintenance requirements [61].

In the Wind Energy Industry, PHM is utilized to monitor the health of wind turbines and predict when maintenance or repair is required. This helps to reduce downtime and increase overall efficiency. GE (General Electric) Renewable Energy has developed a digital system called the "Digital Wind Farm" that employs PHM to optimize wind turbine performance and predict maintenance needs [69].

In Manufacturing, PHM is used to monitor equipment health and predict maintenance needs in real-time, thereby reducing downtime and optimizing production efficiency. General Motors has implemented PHM technology in its manufacturing plants to monitor equipment health and to predict maintenance needs [30].

Errors in data collection can reduce the accuracy of PHM, especially if the data resolution is decreased. While resampling techniques can increase the data resolution, they may also introduce errors. Therefore, the choice of a resampling method should be carefully considered based on the characteristics of the data. [70]

ML algorithms such as decision trees and random forests can handle missing or incomplete data, making them a general solution to this problem. [1]

In certain applications of PHM, transmission delays in the data can lead to incorrect predictions and potentially cause serious safety issues. [26]

2.3 Possible Errors in Data Driven PHM

Data quality is crucial in engineering systems and manufacturing processes since even small inaccuracies in the data can significantly affect the operator's decision-making ability. However, the operators may not have direct access to raw data and may not fully understand its impact on outcomes and subsequent decision-making.

Before Industry 4.0, experienced engineers in each department relied on past experiences to solve problems and develop solutions. However, the process of developing a qualified individual for this role is time-consuming.

Advancements in information and communication technologies are driving significant improvements in data quality and measurement accuracy. However, the sheer volume of data being generated is growing faster than the rate of improvement in data quality. Consequently, many data errors are being produced. For instance, the use of data loggers can lead to various data quality issues, including aliasing and artificial errors such as overload, negatively affecting the accuracy of the RUL estimate and leading to increased maintenance costs.

2.3.1 Impact of F_s and Resolution of Data Generation

The quantity of data packages generated is influenced by two main factors: the F_s and the resolution of the sensors used. F_s determines the rate at which sensors take measurements, while the resolution determines the level of detail or precision of those measurements. Increasing F_s will result in more data being generated, but it may also generate a larger volume of data that could be difficult to manage or analyze. Similarly, increasing the resolution will result in more detailed or precise measurements, but it may also generate a larger volume of data that could be challenging to process or interpret. Therefore, it is crucial to carefully consider the F_s and the resolution of the sensors when designing a data collection system, to balance the need for high-quality data with the need to manage the data effectively. In Section 1.2, corresponding errors, such as F_s reduction, will be induced into the dataset to analyze the impact of these parameters.

2.3.2 Errors in Data Transmission and Storage

Digital data signals can encounter a wide range of errors during transmission and storage. No physical medium can guarantee error-free transmission, and errors can occur due to interference from the transmission environment, artifacts introduced by equipment, or the medium that the data is stored in. Some of the effects that can cause these errors are listed below. [19]

- Thermal noise (Shannon)
- Impulse noise (e.g., arcing relays)
- Signal distortion during transmission (attenuation)
- Crosstalk
- Voice amplitude signal compression (companding)

-
- Quantization noise
 - Jitter (variations in signal timings)
 - Receiver and transmitter out of sync

Errors that are introduced to the data during transmission can be classified as content or flow entity errors. [19]

Content Errors:

Content errors refer to errors in the actual content of a message or data block, rather than errors in the message structure or formatting. For instance, a binary 1 may be transmitted and received as a binary 0. Content errors can occur due to various factors, such as interference, noise, hardware malfunctions, or software bugs. [19]

A burst error is a specific type of content error in which multiple bits in a data block are corrupted or incorrect. The length of a burst error is defined as the number of bits from the first corrupted bit to the last corrupted bit. It is important to note, however, that an error burst may also contain uncorrupted bits, which means that not all of the bits in the burst are necessarily incorrect. Burst errors can occur due to the same factors that cause other types of content errors, and they can have similar effects on the accuracy and reliability of the data. [19]

Flow entity Errors:

The flow of data packets from the source to a destination in a data network can be impacted by several factors. These factors are crucial as they can have significant implications for the performance, reliability, and security of the network. One common factor is congestion, which occurs when too many data packets try to use the same network resources, such as bandwidth or processing power. This leads to delays or interruptions in the flow of data packets, ultimately reducing the overall network performance. Another factor is latency, which refers to the time it takes for a data packet to travel from the source to a destination. High latency results in delays in data transmission. Finally, packet loss is another critical factor that occurs when data packets are lost or dropped during transmission, leading to gaps or holes in the data, which affect its accuracy and completeness. [19]

Error Detecting and Correction:

To identify the presence of errors in a digital signal, error detection codes can be used. These codes consist of supplementary information that is added to a digital data package to perform parity checks. Besides error-detecting codes, error-correcting codes can be used to recover the original message from a corrupted message. Error-correcting codes use the same methodology as error-detecting codes, but they also pinpoint the precise location of the corrupted bit. [21]

2.3.3 Error in ML

The ML process can be impacted by various types of errors that can affect the accuracy of the output. As such, it is crucial for this research project to minimize their impact to ensure the reliability of the ML results, especially given that the input datasets will be compared with each other. These errors can generally be classified into two categories: systematic errors and operational errors.

Aliasing is a phenomenon that occurs when a signal is sampled at a rate lower than its original frequency. In such a scenario, the sampling rate is insufficient to capture all of the signal's details, leading to errors or distortions in the signal. [56]

Low-pass and high-pass filters are commonly used in electronic circuits and signal processing applications to separate or isolate different frequency components of a signal. A low-pass filter removes high frequencies from a signal, while a high-pass filter removes low frequencies. These filters are characterized by their cutoff frequency, the point at which they transition from allowing signals to pass through to blocking or attenuating them. Low-pass filters can be used in conjunction with high-pass filters to create band-pass, band-stop, and notch filters. [5, 20]

Outlier removal is a technique used to identify and remove extreme or unusual values in a dataset. These values can be caused by errors, artifacts, or other anomalies in the data, and they can have a significant impact on the accuracy and reliability of statistical analyses. Statistical methods are used to identify outliers, such as values that are outside of a specified range or that deviate significantly from the overall trend of the data. The removal of outliers can help improve the quality and entity of the dataset. [37]

2.3.4 Risks of High-class imbalanced Data

In a majority-minority classification problem, a skewed distribution of classes in the dataset(s) can significantly affect the performance of classifiers, introducing a prediction bias for the majority class [47] [28].

Class imbalance is a common issue in classification problems when one or a few classes have significantly fewer instances than others, resulting in a highly skewed distribution of instances across different classes. This phenomenon can pose significant challenges to classification algorithms designed to optimize overall accuracy and may prioritize correctly classifying instances from the majority class at the expense of the minority class. As a result, the classification model may exhibit poor performance metrics, such as low recall and F1 score, for the minority class, which can have significant consequences in many real-world applications [79] [67] [28].

To address this issue, various techniques can be used, such as oversampling the minority class, undersampling the majority class, or a combination of both. These methods aim to rebalance the class distribution and reduce the bias towards the majority class, thus improving the performance of the classifier on the minority class. In addition, modifying the cost function to assign higher penalties for misclassification of the minority class, or using ensemble models that combine multiple classifiers, can also be effective in addressing class imbalance [79] [28].

2.4 Overview of Data Mining Algorithms

This section provides a brief introduction to the five most commonly used ML algorithms. These algorithms were selected because they are discussed in the MLA (TU Darmstadt FSR- Machine Learning Application) lecture.

2.4.1 Fine Tree Model

Decision trees, also known as classification trees, are ML algorithms used for regression and classification problems. This algorithm is beneficial in finding relevant features and data patterns. This method works by following a tree-like decision system consisting of a root node, branches, internal nodes, and leaf nodes. Starting from the root node, the process follows the outgoing branches, which connect the root to the internal nodes. In these nodes, the evaluation based on available features is done. Then, next branches feed into the leaf nodes that contain the response. The attributes rule how the tree-like structure will look like, and the goal of this structure is to divide the data into subsets that are as homogeneous as possible. However, this decision scheme is adapted to each particular application case.

For instance, under this project, a Fine Tree model has been contemplated. The particularities of this sub-structure are the existence of several fine distinctions between classes by using many leaves. The last scheme belongs to the type of decision trees named Classification and Regression Trees (CART), and these trees use what is known as the Gini impurity to select the best attribute. This method, together with the information gain method, are the most popular approaches. The principle of the information gain method relies on what is known as entropy, which accounts for the impurity of a given sample with values between 0 and 1. The attribute (dependent variables) that holds the smallest entropy is the one that provides a better split. The way to measure the performance of a given attribute is by using the information gain, which measures the difference in entropy before and after a split on such attribute. Therefore, a higher value in information gain means a greater performance.

Similarly, the Gini impurity accounts for the probability of misclassifying a random data point. Therefore, if the dataset presents a single class, the impurity will become 0.

2.4.2 Naive Bayes Model

Naïve Bayes is a ML algorithm based on Bayesian statistics. Its primary goal is to model the distribution within a specific class for the input data. In contrast to other algorithms like decision trees, which aim to identify the feature that enables higher differentiation between classes, Naïve Bayes works by simplifying conditional probabilities. This simplification involves computing the initial probability (prior probability), which is then updated by the creation of new information to generate an updated probability (posterior probability) [77]. In this model, it is assumed that each feature contributes equally, and a single probability is associated with each variable. To classify an input, the algorithm uses the conditional and prior probabilities to calculate the class with a higher posterior probability [62] as shown in the following equation:

$$\text{Posterior Probability} = \frac{\text{Conditional Probability} \text{Priorprobability}}{\text{Evidence}} \quad (2.1)$$

Furthermore, depending on the type of distribution Naïve Bayes algorithms can be distinguished into different categories; Gaussian Naïve Bayes (assumes a Gaussian distribution), Multinomial Naïve Bayes (uses multinomial distributions) and Bernoulli Naïve Bayes (based on Boolean variables).

Naive Bayes models that do not normalize data can have negative consequences. These include:

-
- **Biased Results:** Naive Bayes assumes that predictor variables (features) are independent of each other. However, if the features are not normalized, some features with larger scales may dominate the prediction process, leading to biased results.[44]
 - **Incorrect Probability Estimates:** Naive Bayes calculates probabilities based on the frequency of each feature in the training data. If the data is not normalized, the frequency of each feature may be distorted, leading to incorrect probability estimates. [17]
 - **Inefficient Model Performance:** Naive Bayes relies on calculating probabilities for each feature, which can be computationally expensive. Normalizing the data can help reduce the number of features that need to be considered, thus improving the model's efficiency. [49]
 - **Overfitting:** Without normalization, the model may overfit on the training data, leading to poor generalization performance on unseen data.[11]

2.4.3 Narrow Neural Network Model

Neural Networks (NN) or Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are algorithms that aim to solve complex decisions by breaking them down into smaller decisions, resulting in a structure similar to the network of human brain neurons. The main elements in this algorithm are nodes, input layers, hidden layers, and an output layer [75]. Each layer is built out of nodes, which are composed of input data, weight, and bias. Weights are grading factors that determine the importance of a given variable. These weights are multiplied by their corresponding input values and summed together. The resulting summation value is transferred to the activation function, which determines an output. If the resulting value surpasses the established threshold, the node will get activated. Then, the data will be allowed to travel from this activated node to the next one, where the described process will be repeated. This process corresponds to a Feed Forward Neural Network (FFNN), which is the most commonly used type of NN. However, data transmission processes [2] and the type of NN can vary for each application [66].

In this project, for example, Narrow Neural Networks (NNN) are implemented. NNNs are structured with a minimal representation of hidden layers [45]. This approach aims to build a more understandable scheme and save computational time.

Not normalizing data when using NNNs may cause poor classification performance [7], inefficient feature selection [63], and an unbalanced contribution of features [46].

2.4.4 k-Nearest Neighbors Model

The K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN) method can be used for regression or classification problems. The algorithm aims to determine the value of a given variable based on available information, i.e., the given data points (nearest neighbours). In classification, when new data is inputted, the algorithm takes a sample of the existing data points within a range and evaluates the predominant class. This class is associated with the provided input data. Similarly, for regression, instead of finding the predominant class, the algorithm computes the average value of the data points within the sample. Therefore, the sample size and range are critical factors in determining the value or class of a dependent variable. There are various methods to determine the range, such as the Euclidean distance, which measures the straight line between the given point and other points [10, 29].

The number (k) of data points (neighbours) taken to conduct the evaluation is also a crucial factor. The optimization of k is highly dependent on the application case and a topic of research. Various approaches, such as the optimization method proposed by Catapang [36], can be used to determine this value. However, the basics can be summarized using variance and bias. Selecting a high value of k results in low bias and high variance, which increases the likelihood of overfitting. In contrast, low values of k lead to an underfitting model with high bias and low variance [33].

2.4.5 Support Vector Machines Model

The Support Vector Machines (SVM) algorithm is suitable for both regression and classification problems. The method works by finding the boundary between data categories mapped by a hyperplane [34]. To illustrate this concept, consider a two-dimensional dataset in which a straight line separates the two classes. SVM then defines marginal lines that determine the distance between the classes. The algorithm maximizes the margin distance, as a large margin improves the classification accuracy by reducing the likelihood of miss classification. SVM uses existing data points lying on the margin lines, known as support vectors, to set the margins.

The optimization of SVM through margin distance can take different forms [55] and is an ongoing topic of research. The optimization problem is to find the right balance between miss classification and margin dimension. A higher margin leads to better classification, but in some cases, it may result in miss classification of certain data points.

SVM can be applied to various use cases. However, datasets often have complex distributions, making it difficult to define a good boundary using a straight line. In such cases, the feature space is transformed using a mathematical function called a kernel. This transformation introduces a higher dimensional space into the original feature space, enabling the separation of data into classes [54].

2.5 Evaluation Methods

A confusion matrix is a table used to evaluate the performance of a classification model in ML. It summarizes the predictions of a model compared to the actual ground truth. For binary classification problems, the matrix is usually of size 2×2 , where each row represents the instances in a predicted class and each column represents the instances in an actual class. The four cells of the matrix represent True Positive (TP), False Positive (FP), False Negative (FN), and True Negative (TN). The confusion matrix provides valuable information about the performance of a model, such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score.

Precision, recall, accuracy, and F1 score are defined as the following equations

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (2.2)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (2.3)$$

$$F1 = \frac{2 \times \text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (2.4)$$

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FN + TN + FP} \quad (2.5)$$

Precision is a metric that measures the accuracy of positive predictions by determining the number of positive predicted samples that are actually positive. Recall is specific to the original sample and indicates how many of the positive cases were predicted correctly. Precision and recall are often seen as contradictory since a high precision means a low recall, and vice versa.

The F1 score is a metric that combines precision and recall into a single score, providing a balanced evaluation of a binary classification model's performance. It is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, ranging from 0 to 1, with higher scores indicating better performance.

Accuracy is the percentage of correctly classified samples out of the total number of samples and reflects the classifier's decision-making ability.

The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve is a composite indicator that reflects the continuous variable of FP and TP. The ROC curve's horizontal axis represents the FP rate, where a higher value indicates more actual negative samples predicted as positive. The vertical axis represents the TP rate, where a higher value indicates more positive samples predicted as positive.

AUC (Area Under Curve) is the area under the ROC curve and is used as a metric for evaluating the performance of binary classification models. The AUC metric can be used to evaluate the performance of a binary classification model. A perfect classifier would have an AUC of 1, indicating that it can make perfect predictions regardless of the parameter. An AUC between 0.5 and 1 is considered better than random classification, meaning the classifier has some predictive value when the parameter is set appropriately. An AUC of 0.5 is the same as random classification and indicates that the model has no predictive value. A model with an AUC less than 0.5 is worse than random classification, but it can still be better than random guessing as long as the predictions are always reversed.

3 Methodology

In this chapter, high-level guidance on how the project has proceeded, as well as several project management concepts to narrow down the project scope, the determination of the ML model, the trade-offs of evaluation methods, and the verification and validation concepts have been discussed.

3.1 Concept of Operation of the Final Design

The project's workflow design follows the CRISP-DM (Cross-industry standard process for data mining) methodology, but with some customized adjustments to meet the project's specific requirements. The workflow comprises three main stages: *Data Understanding*, *ML*, and *Evaluation*, as shown in figure A.1.

1. Find a dataset that meets the required characteristics.
2. Clean and denoise the data.
3. Identify possible errors that could occur in the system.
4. Research commonly used algorithms in system monitoring.
5. Compare the performance of different models and select the best one.
6. Reduce the F_s of the dataset.
7. Define and generate different types of data corruption caused by transmission delay.
8. Feed the corrupted datasets into the trained ML models.
9. Establish an accuracy benchmark for evaluating error propagation in the models.
10. Compare the accuracy obtained from the corrupted data to the standard benchmark.
11. Validate the performance of the models by examining the absolute AUC.
12. Interpret the results obtained from the data error.
13. Identify areas for further improvement.

3.2 Defining the Scope of the Project

To define the project's scope, it is divided into the following sections: levels of success, design requirements, functional requirements, critical project elements, problem determination, and work breakdown structure. These sections provide guidelines for the development and evaluation of the project.

Level of Success

In Figure A.6 provides a summary of the project's success levels. These levels are categorized into three main areas: data understanding, data preparation/modeling, and evaluation. There are three levels in total, with Level 1 representing the minimum requirement, Level 2 representing desired achievement, and Level 3 offering a better than expected version of the design.

Design Requirements, Functional Requirements and Critical Project Elements

The design requirements, functional requirements, and critical project elements are presented in figure A.3, A.4, and A.5, respectively. FSR's task sheet specifies four design requirements, which the team addressed through eight functional requirements. The project has five critical project elements, which were also addressed through eight functional requirements.

Problem Determination

The input data for the ML model is flight-pass dataset, which consists of numerical values such as voltage, current, and temperature. The output of the ML model is a categorical variable, which classifies the system as either healthy or faulty. Therefore, the classification method is suitable for this project, as Figure A.2 shown.

Work Breakdown Structure

Figure A.8 illustrates the work breakdown structure of the project, which is divided into three main areas: Objectives Requirements, ML, and Evaluation. Each of these areas consists of several core tasks that need to be completed.

3.3 Determination of Data Mining Algorithms

The table 3.1 presents the advantages and disadvantages of various ML models, which can be utilized in both regression and classification methods. This qualitative classification serves as a guideline for the initial filtering step to distinguish the most promising algorithms from the rest in the context of the system under study. After the pre-selection, a quantitative ranking is established based on parameters such as computation time, accuracy of the test data, F1 of the test data, and AUC of the test data.

Table 3.1: Trade Matrix of Supervised ML Algorithms Selection

ML Algorithms	Advantages	Disadvantages
Decision Tree Classification	Interpretability, no need for feature scaling Works on both linear / non-linear problems	Poor results on very small datasets Overfitting can easily occur
Support Vector Machine	Pre-format, not biased by outliers Not sensitive to over-fitting	Not appropriate for non-linear problems Not the best choice for a large number of features
Naive Bayes	Efficient Not biased by outliers works on non-linear problems, probabilistic approach	Based on the assumption that the features have the same statistical relevance
K-Nearest Neighbors	Simple to understand Fast and efficient	Need to manually choose the number of neighbors ' k '
Narrow Neural Network	Good to model with nonlinear data with a large number of inputs. Once trained, the predictions are pretty fast. Can be trained with any number of inputs and layers. Neural networks work best with more data points.	Black boxes methodology, meaning we cannot know how much each independent variable is influencing the dependent variables It is computationally very expensive and time consuming to train with traditional CPUs High dependence on training data. This leads to overfitting and generalization

The ranking of the resulting models after training is shown in table 3.2, with the Fine Tree algorithm being the best performing. However, it should be noted that the K-Nearest Neighbours and SVM algorithms were not considered further due to their high computational time. These models took more than 48 hours to train and yet did not yield any results, even though they were trained using MATLAB Classification Learner on a laptop with 2.6 GHz 6-Core Intel Core i7 and 16 GB 2667 MHz DDR4 memory.

Table 3.2: Ranking of the selected Supervised ML Algorithms

ML Algorithms Ranking			
Computing time	Accuracy of Test	F1 of Test	AUC of the Test
Tree < NB << NNN	Tree > NNN > NB	Tree > NNN > NB	Tree > NNN > NB

3.4 Trade-off of Evaluation Methods

Model evaluation, model selection, and algorithm selection play important roles in ML. Several evaluation methods are commonly used to generalize to unseen data, improve model performance, and identify the best model, such as the area under the curve (AUC), confusion matrix, accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and consideration of data distribution.

Table 3.3: Evaluation Methods

Trade Matrix of Evaluation Methods		
Evaluation Method	Pros	Cons
AUC	Possible to make a reasonable evaluation of the classifier in the case of unbalanced samples Very intuitive	Essentially the measurement of the order of the predictions Only care about whether the probability of any positive sample is greater than the probability of a negative sample
Confusion matrix	Identify class imbalances in the training data Can be used with any type of classification model	No information about the cause of errors Not useful for models with a large number of classes
F1 Score	High accuracy with unbalanced data Does not reveal mutual information between features Comprehensive evaluation of precision and recall	Difficult to interpret Reveal nothing about the combination of the two features
Data distribution	Visually strong Easy to compare data	Extremely focus on the number of "bins" Heavily affected by the maximum and minimum of the variable
Accuracy	Useful measurement when the amount of samples per class is the same	Fail if the classes are imbalanced Have issues when the classes are naturally balanced
Precision	Reflect what proportion of positive classifications are correct	Precision deals with true positives and false positives Measures never take true negatives into account
Recall	Reflect what proportion of actual positives are identified correctly	Recall deals with true positives and false negatives Measures never take true negatives into account

4 Final Design

This chapter presents the final detailed design of the project, including the technical implementation of CONOPS (Concept of Operation), which is a functional block diagram, ML input, ML output, ML with uncorrupted training data, data quality corruption methods, and ML with corrupted training data.

4.1 Overview of the Final Design

A functional block diagram (figure 4.1) provides a detailed technical implementation of the CONOPS, and the details of each block are shown in the following section.

ML Input:

To facilitate ML, an open-source dataset was initially sought, however all of the datasets found did not meet the project's requirements. Therefore, synthetic datasets were created using various tools, including "Circuit Lab", "Multisim", "MatLab", and "Simulink." Eventually, MATLAB with Simulink was selected for its versatility and availability of the full program. This approach allowed for easy loading and unloading of data within one program.

To simulate real-life conditions, an AC motor was used as it was the closest available component. The circuit included a variable-resistor to modify the resistance value in a DC circuit, an ideal inverter to convert the signal to AC, and various output sensors for current, voltage, velocity, and shaft angle. The initial circuit lacked noise but was later modified to include noise for both input and output, additional sensors (e.g., temperature), and a feedback system that utilized output sensors.

Ten runs of the circuit were conducted, and the resulting data were combined to create a single dataset.

ML Output:

The output section begins by collecting the dataset generated in the previous step, namely, "ML Input." However, upon analyzing this final dataset, it was found to be highly predictable. To interrupt this predictability, it was decided to change the output of the dataset by modifying the levels of "healthy" and "unhealthy" data. Two possible approaches were considered for this purpose.

The first approach involved a manual labeling process that relied on the standard deviation parameter as the decision factor. This involved comparing the obtained values (voltage [V], current [I], etc.) with three times their standard deviation. The second approach was to directly modify the output column of the dataset by a certain percentage. Ultimately, the latter approach was chosen, with a correction factor of 5 percent. This method was preferred since it resulted in a new dataset with corrupted output that would serve as a benchmark for analyzing the behavior of the model when working with corrupted data.

ML and Data Corruption:

At this stage, the target of the ML algorithms is the previously defined benchmark (column of output). The selected algorithms (Fine Tree, Naive Bayes, and Narrow Neural Network) are trained. In further analysis of variable selection, time was excluded as a parameter due to conflicts with transmission delay M2.

Next, errors will be introduced into the dataset by reducing the F_s , implementing transmission delay, or a combination of both. Three different transmission delay methods (M1, M2, and M3) will be used. It will be interesting to observe how the diagnostics performance behaves when trained with corrupted data. In this case, the corrupted data will be used in four different ways as training data to build the model and make predictions, as before, and then with the data coming from transmission delay M1, M2, and M3.

Evaluation:

The evaluation methods used in this project are AUC, confusion matrix, accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and histogram of data distribution. AUC is the primary evaluation metric, and the other methods are used partially.

When evaluating the transmission delay or reducing F_s methods, the original AUC value without any data corruption is examined first. An original AUC value of approximately 0.6 or 0.7 is desirable for the project's purposes. In some cases, the normalized AUC may bounce back slightly. The maximum corruption tolerance is determined by identifying the first lowest point of the AUC value. It's important to note that such bounce back cases are rare and may be classified as false positives.

Given that the project focuses on PHM system monitoring, detecting anomalies is crucial. Therefore, it's essential to ensure that the model is sensitive enough to detect anomalies.

Figure 4.1: Functional Block Diagram

4.2 Identification and Creation of a Dataset

Data acquisition posed a challenge for this project due to the specific characteristics required. High frequency, a large dataset, a relatively large number of variables, some with correlation to a goal, and data that changes with time (e.g., RUL) were all necessary. The frequency needed to be at least 20 kHz, with a dataset of at least 5-10 million lines and multiple runs being advantageous. A minimum of four variables was required, but more variables were better as they increase the chance of strong correlations necessary for the ML process and similar to the model being compared to.

Unfortunately, publicly available data rarely meets all these requirements, leading to the decision to seek a new solution through synthetic data. MATLAB with Simulink was used to simulate an AC motor and create the necessary data.

4.2.1 Data Acquisition via Open Source data

The datasets were primarily sourced from “Kaggle,” a large open-source repository of datasets. However, despite its size, none of the datasets met all the project requirements. Most of the datasets found on Kaggle were consistently too small. Additional datasets were sourced from various other sources. To evaluate each dataset, a point scoring system was developed that assessed the type, source, frequency, and number of variables in each dataset.

Table 4.2: Weight of dataset Categories

Type of Dataset	Data source	Frequency	Number of Variables
Weight:	0.325	0.225	0.325
			0.125

Table 4.3 shows how points were awarded, table 4.2 shows the weight of each category, and table 4.4 shows the points earned by each dataset. A complete list of the datasets can be found in table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Found datasets

Source	Number	Title	Source
Github Links			
	GH1	MAFAULDA. Machinery Fault Database [...]	[23]
	GH2	NASA Bearing dataset	[73]
	GH6	Bearing Vibration Data under Time-varying [...]	[31]
	GH7	Planetary gearbox vibration data	[18]
	GH8	Condition Monitoring for Handpumps [...]	[25]
	GH9	Unbalance Classification Using Vibration [...]	[51]
	GH10	AI4I 2020 Predictive Maintenance dataset [...]	[74]
	GH11	Microsoft Azure Predictive Maintenance	[6]
Team Found			
	TF1	Electric Motor Temperature	[42]
	TF2	Prognosis based on Varying Data Quality	
	TF3	Condition Monitoring of Hydraulic Systems	[3]
	TF4	NASA Turbofan Jet Engine dataset	[8]
	TF5	Gearbox Fault Diagnosis	[12]
	TF6	Predictive Useful Life based into telemetry	[80]
	TF7	Gearbox Fault Detection Dataset, PHM Data [...]	[38]
	TF8	"CMap"	
	TF9	Power Quality Classification Dataset - 1	[43]
	TF10	eVTOL Battery Dataset	[22]
	TF11	Data-driven prediction of battery cycle life [...]	
	TF12	UK Domestic Appliance-Level Electricity [...]	[40]
	TF13	PHM Data Challenge	[35]
	TF14	IDMT-ISA-ELECTRIC-ENGINE	[64]
Team Made			
	TM1	Simulink Basic First Iteration	
	TM2	Simulink Final Iteration	

Table 4.3: dataset Points Given

Type of Dataset	Data source	Frequency	Number of Variables
Electrical: 100	Syntetic: 75	100kHz+: 100	100*Number/Highest
Mechanical: 50	Real System: 100	75-100kHz: 75	
	Vibration: 75	50-75kHz: 50	
		25-50kHz: 25	
		10-25kHz: 10	
		<10kHz: 0	

Table 4.4: dataset Points

Dataset Name	Type of Dataset	Data source	Frequency	Number of Variables	Overall score
GH1	50	75	10		36.375
GH2	75	70	0	8	43.8287037
GH7	50	75		9	37.29166667
GH10	50	75	0	14	39.60648148
GH11	50	100	0	4	40.60185185
TF2	0	0	0	4	1.851851852
TF3	50	100	0	17	46.62037037
TF4	50	75	0	27	45.625
TF5	50	75	0		33.125
TF6	50	75	0	10	37.75462963
TF7	50	75	0	2	34.05092593
TF9	80	75	0	9	47.04166667
TF10	80	100	0	10	53.12962963
TF11	80	100	10	10	56.37962963
TF12	80	100	10	5	54.06481481
TF13	75	100		24	57.98611111
TF14	80	75	25		51
TM1	100	75	25	7	60.74074074
TM2	100	75	25	17	65.37037037

4.2.2 MATLAB Overview and Workflow

An overview of the workflow for the simulation can be viewed in figure 4.2 and it begins in MATLAB with the creation of a “flightpath”, followed by the addition of noise and data spikes. Using equation 4.1 and table 4.5, simulation values that are needed in Simulink are generated, but importantly, these values are not considered part of the input. A script then runs to bring all the values and the input into the simulation and then finally the simulation runs. This process is repeated 10 times to create a dataset that is 10,000,010 lines long and has a frequency of 25 kHz. The Simulink simulates an AC motor that is deteriorating over time. This is done by supplying a value that becomes the resistance in a DC circuit, which then is converted into an AC circuit to be feed into the motor, which in turn produces mechanical values which are stored and used as feedback.

Figure 4.2: MATLAB Block Diagram

4.2.3 MATLAB Scripts of generating Flightpath, Noise, Wind, and Randomness

The first script generates a random "flightpath," which represents the simulated input to the system. This flightpath is an arbitrary current value that will later be inverted to a resistance value to control the DC circuit, using Ohm's Law. The flightpath models the different stages of flight in relation to the engine power needed, including initial start-up, take-off, decrease in power 1, steady cruise flight, decrease in power 2, constant landing power, and final power down. Each simulation runs for a total of 40 seconds, with the time split up among each stage based on a random value multiplied by a deviation and added to a median value (equation 4.1). The median values and deviations for each stage can be found in table 4.5.

For the cruise stage, any leftover time is used to bring the total time to 40 seconds (equation 4.2). The "rand" function is used to generate a pseudo-random value between 0 and 1 [16] to determine the takeoff, cruise, and landing resistance values. Percentages are used for the calculations to increase flexibility. The timing is based on the stages of flight, with adjustments made to ensure stability and that no segment is too short. The script results in a linear piecewise function, and figures 4.3 and 4.4 show statistical plots across 2000 outputs. The statistics were calculated timestamp by timestamp; for instance, the mean value at the 20-second mark is the mean value across all 2000 generated plots at that point.

$$\text{Final Value} = \text{Random Value} * \text{Deviation} - \frac{\text{Deviation}}{2} + \text{Median Value} \quad (4.1)$$

$$t_{\text{cruise}} = 40\text{seconds} - (t_{\text{revup}} + t_{\text{takeoff}} + t_{\text{revdown1}} + t_{\text{revdown2}} + t_{\text{landing}} + t_{\text{revdown3}}) \quad (4.2)$$

Table 4.5: Values Used for Randomization

Script	Variable	Median	Deviation (from MATLAB)	Real Deviation
Random_Flight	Initial Start-Up (%.a.D)	0.01	0.001	0.0005
	Takeoff Value	700	200	100
	Takeoff Time (%.a.D)	0.055	0.03	0.015
	Deceleration 1 Time (%.a.D)	0.0075	0.004	0.002
	Cruise Value (%.a.D)	0.7	0.1	0.05
	Deceleration 2 Time (%.a.D)	0.0075	0.004	0.002
	Landing Value (%.a.D)	0.268181818	0.1	0.05
	Landing Time (%.a.D)	0.15	0.1	0.05
	Deceleration 3 Time (%.a.D)	0.01	0.01	0.005
Noise	Noise Deviation	60	30	15
Wind	q	0	4	2
Random_Values	Angular Weight	0.0000672	0.000007	0.0000035
	Angular Weight Exponet	2.75	0.5	0.25
	Velocity Weight	0.00112	0.000116667	5.83333E-05
	Temp 1 Weight	1.80706E-06	1.88235E-07	9.41176E-08
	Temp 2 Weight	0.000200784	2.0915E-05	1.04575E-05
	Kill	0.28	0.06	0.03
	FPm	1.65	0.3	0.15
	FCm	0.045	0.03	0.015
Sensor_Noise	A Noise	500	500	250
	V Noise	100	100	50
	T Noise	10	10	5
	Voltage DC Noise	30	30	15
	Current DC Noise	100	100	50
	Voltage AC Noise	30	30	15
	Current AC Noise	50	50	25
	Heat Stator A Noise	30	30	15
	Heat Stator B Noise	30	30	15
	Heat Stator C Noise	30	30	15
	Heat Rotor Noise	30	30	15

Figure 4.3: 10 Randomly Generated Base Flightpaths

Figure 4.4: Statistical Stats across 2000 Base Flightpaths

The next script to run is the first of the noise scripts. The script utilizes the function "randn" to generate a pseudo-random matrix with a Gaussian distribution. To bring the mean of this generation closer to zero, the mean of the matrix is subtracted from each value in the generated matrix (see equation 4.3). A random deviation is then generated using the values from table 4.5 and the equation in 4.1. Using this deviation, the original matrix is modified by setting its bounds to the deviation. This is achieved by dividing the maximum and minimum values of the matrix by the generated deviation, taking the higher of the two values, and then dividing the noise matrix by that value (see equations 4.4 to 4.6).

To make the noise matrix non-Gaussian, the function "MBHTM" is applied. This function, sourced from the Mathworks community pages by user "E. Cheynet", takes the Gaussian distributed matrix, a skew value of 0.5, and a Kurtosis value of 4. The MBHTM function then computes a non-Gaussian distributed matrix using a moment-based Hermite transformation model and a cubic transform. The non-Gaussian noise is then modified again using the same process as in equations 4.4 to 4.6. Finally, the non-Gaussian noise is added onto the previously generated flightpath to create a new flightpath.

A comparison of a single randomly generated noise matrix is shown in figures 4.5 through 4.9. The values before and after the non-Gaussian change are sorted numerically to create a curve and show the distribution of weight. A Gaussian function has nearly perfect symmetry in this graph, whereas the non-Gaussian should be skewed. Figures 4.6 and 4.7 show the graphs overlaid after 20 seconds to visually compare the difference. Figures 4.8 and 4.9 plot the differences between each half of the graph to compare against each other.

$$\text{Noise}_1 = \text{Noise}_0 - \text{mean}(\text{Noise}_0) \quad (4.3)$$

$$\text{Noise}_{\text{Max}} = \left| \frac{\max(\text{Noise}_1)}{\text{Noise}_{\text{Deviation}}} \right| \quad (4.4)$$

$$\text{Noise}_{\text{Min}} = \left| \frac{\min(\text{Noise}_1)}{\text{Noise}_{\text{Deviation}}} \right| \quad (4.5)$$

$$\text{Noise}_2 = \begin{cases} \frac{\text{Noise}_1}{\text{Noise}_{\text{Min}}} & \text{Noise}_{\text{Max}} < \text{Noise}_{\text{Min}} \\ \frac{\text{Noise}_1}{\text{Noise}_{\text{Max}}} & \text{Noise}_{\text{Max}} \geq \text{Noise}_{\text{Min}} \end{cases} \quad (4.6)$$

Figure 4.5: Sorted Noise Values for Noise Input

Figure 4.6: Symmetry Comparison of Gaussian Noise for Noise Input

Figure 4.7: Symmetry Comparison of Nongaussian Noise for Noise Input

Figure 4.8: Difference in Symmetry for Noise for Noise Input

Figure 4.9: Difference in Symmetry for Noise as a Percentage to Max Difference for Noise Input

The following script adds “Wind” to the simulation. The script simulates needing more or less engine power by adding randomly generated spikes. Skewed bell curves are used to generate these spikes, with a minimum peak of 30 Ohms and a maximum peak of 110 Ohms (when the skew is 0). The formula used is a simplified bell curve formula bounded by -3 to 3 (equation 4.7). The shape of the waves can be seen in figures: B.1, B.2, B.3, B.4, B.5, B.6, B.7 and B.8. A matrix the same size as the flightpath is generated using the “rand” function to determine the position and total amount of spikes. Each line in the flightpath has a 0.0003% chance to be a positive spike and a 0.00025% chance to be a negative spike. After 100,000 sample runs, the characteristics of the number of waves can be viewed in figure 4.10 and table 4.6. The waves do not have an equal chance to appear at any position. Waves that go over an edge are shifted to completely fit inside the “flightpath” because the code would not function with non-completed waves either end. Therefore, there’s a slightly higher chance a wind spike will appear near the end, and there is zero chance of a non-completed wave. The shift involves moving the wave to be at least half a wavelength away from either end. Equations used are 4.8 and 4.9, and figures B.10, B.11 and B.9 depict the positioning of waves. Where the slope is lower, there is an increased chance of a

Table 4.6: Wind Characteristics

	LP	LN	Ratio (LN/LP)
Chance	0.000003	0.0000025	0.833333333
Mean	2.99633	2.49999	0.834350689
Median	3	2	0.666666667
Max	13	12	0.923076923

wave appearing relative to everywhere else. These figures show that there is an increased chance near the edge compared to everywhere else. They also show the start and end of the waves to indicate where the influence of a wave would end. Finally, waves can be superimposed onto each other, without regard to sign, but a perfect overlap of positive and negative waves is not possible.

$$\text{Wind} = S * e^{-\frac{\pi * t^2}{2}} (1 + q * t), t = [-3, 3] \quad (4.7)$$

$$\text{Wind}_{\text{Center Point},1} = \begin{cases} \text{Wind}_{\text{Center Point},0} + \frac{F_s * \lambda}{2} & \text{Wind}_{\text{Center Point},0} \leq \frac{F_s * \lambda}{2} \\ \text{Wind}_{\text{Center Point},0} & \text{Wind}_{\text{Center Point},0} > \frac{F_s * \lambda}{2} \end{cases} \quad (4.8)$$

$$\text{Wind}_{\text{Center Point},1} = \begin{cases} \text{Wind}_{\text{Center Point},0} - \frac{F_s * \lambda}{2} & \text{Wind}_{\text{Center Point},0} \geq \frac{\text{Time}_{\text{Max}} F_s * \lambda}{2} \\ \text{Wind}_{\text{Center Point},0} & \text{Wind}_{\text{Center Point},0} < \frac{\text{Time}_{\text{Max}} F_s * \lambda}{2} \end{cases} \quad (4.9)$$

Figure 4.10: Frequency of Wind Spikes Per Run Across 100,000 Runs

Figure 4.11: Positioning of Both Positive and Negative Waves Across 2000 Runs

The next script is called the “Random Value” script, and its purpose is to generate randomized values for the simulation. The values are generated following the same procedure used in the first script, which involves using equation 4.1. The values used in the process are logged in table 4.5.

Following the “Random Value” script is the “Sensor Noise” script, which adds noise to the output of the simulation to make the sensors non-perfect. This process starts by applying equation 4.1 and selecting the amount of noise per sensor using the values in table 4.5. The actual noise is generated using the “rand” function and a gaussian to non-gaussian function called “MBHTM.m”. This process is very similar to the one used in the first “Noise” script.

The next script is the “Pre-Simulation” script, which loads all of the simulation values, noise, and the input “flightpath”. Additionally, this script inverts the input to control the motor using the resistance instead of the current. This is necessary because Simulink does not allow the use of a "variable current source", which requires a workaround that involves using the relationship between voltage, current, and resistance.

Finally, the last script needed to finish the simulation is the “Post-Simulation” script. This script extracts the output values from the simulation, applies the “Sensor Noise”, and combines all of the data into a usable matrix that can be used for ML.

4.2.4 Overview of Flightpath Circuit

The circuit used for the simulation is a single Simulink circuit that produces a matrix that can be modified for ML purposes. The complete circuit is depicted in figure B.12 and a simplified block diagram in figure 4.12. The information flow through the circuit commences at the input, located at the center of the circuit, as shown in figure B.13. The flightpath is loaded into the flight variable and inserted into the “Flight Input” block, as displayed in figure B.14. This block multiplies the input by a weight that enables the circuit to operate. The result is then added to a "sum" block, which provides feedback at the end. The value of resistance is decreased by a factor of 0.8 and saved as a variable resistor. This value is used as the resistance in the first part of the electrical system (in Ohms).

Figure 4.12: Block Diagram of the Circuit

The electrical system starts with the variable resistor mentioned earlier. The electrical circuits can be viewed in figures B.15 to B.19. Figure B.15 provides an overview of the circuit. The current flows from the resistor into the DC system, then into an "Average-Value Inverter", followed by an AC system, and finally into the "Induction Machine Squirrel Cage" (a Squirrel Cage AC motor). The values used in the circuit are shown in 4.7. Figure B.16 illustrates the details of the DC system, including an ideal voltage and current sensor, the voltage source (600 V in DC), and scopes for the sensors in the "DC Scope" block (figure B.17). The AC system in figures B.18 and B.19 is similar to the DC system in that it uses ideal sensors and outputs values into scopes and as variables. Finally, the current is introduced into the "Induction Machine Squirrel Cage", and the values used are shown in 4.7.

Table 4.7: Simulink Constants

Componet	Variable	Value	Unit
Programmable Voltage Source	DC Voltage	600	V
	Average-Value Inverter		
	Rated AC Frequency	60	Hz
	Phase Shift	0	deg
	Ratio of Rated AC Voltage to rated DC voltage	sqrt(6)/pi	
	Fixed Power Loss	1.00E+03	W
	DC Voltage for Turn On	100	V
	DC Voltage for Turn Off	75	V
Induction Machine Squirrel Cage	Rated Apparent Power	1.50E+04	A*V
	Rated Voltage	660	V
	Rated Electrical Frequency	60	Hz
	Number of Pole Pairs	1	
	Parameterizaition Unit	SI	
	Stator Resistance	0.25	Ohm
	Stator Leakage Reactance	0.4	Ohm
	Referred Rotor Resistance	0.14	Ohm
	Referred Rotor Leakage Reactance	0.41	Ohm
	Magnetizing Reactance	17	Ohm
	Stator Zero-Sequence Reactance	0.4	Ohm
	Measurement Temperature	298.15	K
	Resistance Temperature Coefficient	3.93E-08	1/K
	Cage Resistance Temperature Coefficient	4.40E-08	1/K
	Thermal Mass for Each Stator Winding	100	J/K
		Rotor Thermal Mass	200
	Inertia	0.025	kg*m ²
Rotational Friction	Breakaway Friction Torque	25	N*m
	Breakaway Friction Velocity	0.1	rad/s
	Coulomb Friction Torque	20	N*m
	Viscous Friction Coefficient	0.005	N*m*s/rad
Solver Configuration	Equation Formulation	Time	
	Consistency Tolerance	1.00E-09	
	Solver Type	Backward Euler	
	Sample Time	1/25000	

The motor output is shown in B.20, which displays six variables: "R," "C," "HA," "HB," "HC," and "HR." "R" represents a virtual rotating rod, and "C" is the conservative port, used as a reference for the motor. "HA," "HB," and "HC" represent the heat from the stators of the motor, stators A through C, respectively. "HR" represents the heat from the rotor. The solver block is the most important block in this section, and it provides an endpoint to the system and where the system is trying to solve. The values for this block are also available in 4.7. After the motor and solver block, the "R" variable is processed through the "Mechanical Sensors" block (figure B.21). This block uses an "Ideal Torque Sensor" and adds inertia and rotational friction, both of which are essential for limiting and helping the system perform predictably. The block also employs an "Ideal Rotational Motion Sensor." The scopes for these variables are in figures B.22 and B.23. The final block in this section is the "Temperature Scopes" block, which houses the temperature sensor, temperature reference, and scope for all four heat values leaving the motor (figure

B.24). The values found here are then put through "GoTo" blocks to be used in the feedback system.

The feedback system is depicted in figure B.25. The system comprises 13 "From" blocks that provide input values to the feedback system. The "Feedback" block (figure B.26) includes four sub-blocks: the temperature effect (figure B.27), the torque effect (figure B.28), the angle effect (figure B.29), and the velocity effect (figure B.30). The purpose of using these effects is to leverage various cause and effect relationships and the different shaped graphs they generate, which contribute to the feedback effect. The temperature effect is computed by taking the average of the temperatures from the three stators, multiplying the result by a weight, and adding it to the temperature of the rotor, which is also multiplied by a weight. The angle weight is determined by converting the rad unit to rotations, multiplying it by a weight, raising it to a randomly generated value, and then reweighing it. Similarly, the velocity effect is calculated by converting it to rotations per second, multiplying it by a weight, and summing it with other effects. Once all the effects are calculated, they are combined and sent to the "Internal Break Detection" block (figures B.13 and B.31). The goal of the break detection block is to generate a goal output. During different iterations of the system, once the system is "broken," the block would continue to "break" the system further. The system starts with a switch that connects to a goal switch and a "break switch." All switches use the same "kill" value, and once the value is reached, the goal output switches from 0 to 1 and adds the "old value" to the "new" as the system runs. Once the system is broken, it cannot be unbroken. Finally, after the detection block, the circuit adds the resistance from the feedback with the flight input to continue the loop.

4.3 Determination of Labelling

In this chapter, several solutions for determining the ML output have been considered, and the ML output with the best performance has been determined based on its performance in both data science and real-life applications.

4.3.1 Truth Output generated from Flightpath

The truth output is derived from the flightpath, as shown in Figure 4.13. The figure illustrates an imbalance in the truth output, with a ratio of 5.33% of faulty class to healthy class. This suggests that the truth output is highly predictive. Each flightpath is marked as faulty and remains in that state until the end of the flightpath, without oscillating between faulty and healthy states. This limitation is due to the circuit design, as stated earlier, and once the system is broken, it cannot be unbroken. Therefore, the ML algorithm does not need to make any effort to predict the response as long as it returns the healthy class, given the heavily imbalanced data.

Figure 4.13: Data Distribution of Truth Output

The figure depicted in Figure B.32 illustrates that the majority of variables in the dataset have a correlation coefficient value of approximately 0.3 with respect to the truth output. The dataset comprises 18 variables; however, the first three variables, which are run numbers indicating flight path, time variables ranging from 0-40s repeated ten times, and flight indicating flight phase, were excluded from the ML correlation analysis since they are independent of the truth output. Given the data imbalance, various approaches were tested to balance the output data.

To provide meaningful insights from ML analysis, further investigation was carried out without relying on the truth output. Figure B.33 depicts the results of ML using selected models with only 1 flightpath, which resulted in high accuracy, precision, and recall despite the output imbalance.

4.3.2 Manual Label Output by Specification of Measurement Restrictions

To determine the state of the system, a threshold method can be used where the output is manually labeled. Operational thresholds are set for each variable to determine whether the system state is healthy or faulty. If the values of the variables fall outside the range of operating threshold values, the system state is considered faulty. Conversely, if the measured values fall within the operating threshold range, the current state is associated with a healthy state.

The resulting thresholds for selected variables, including DC current, AC voltage, AC current, torque, and angular momentum, are shown in Figure 4.8. If the recorded value exceeds its upper or lower limit,

it is marked as faulty. However, for torque, the average value is used as the boundary condition instead of the standard deviation. Therefore, values higher than its average represent a healthy state, while lower values indicate a faulty state.

Table 4.8: Threshold Method

	Var5 (DC current)	Var7 (AC Voltage)	Var8 (AC Current)	Var11 (Torque)	Var17 (Angular Momentum)
Average	890.9613	295.8193	603.1981	21.6883	2.1524e5
Standard Deviation σ	153.1709	138.2101	100.0386	4.5269	5.2317e4
Upper Bound $avg+3*\sigma$	1.3505e3	710.4495	903.3140	35.2691	3.7219e5
Lower Bound $avg-3*\sigma$	431.4486	-118.811	303.0822	8.1076	5.829e4

The variables selected for analysis were chosen based on customer requirements and the project’s usability. DC current, AC voltage, and AC current were directly requested by the customer to ensure the final results of the project are applicable. Additionally, the presence of a DC voltage source, inverter, and AC motor are mandatory requirements under ETHAN’s framework. Torque and angular momentum are typical parameters studied when choosing a motor, and their analysis is relevant to this project.

Figure 4.14: Logic Gate for Manual Labelling

The threshold method implemented in this project operates using a logic circuit that utilizes the measure of 3σ as a limit. As shown in Figure 4.14, AC voltage and current are combined using an OR logic gate, which means that if either of these measures exceeds the limit, the output of the gate will be faulty. Conversely, torque and angular momentum are combined by an AND gate, which requires both values to exceed the limits for the output to be classified as faulty. Finally, all three outputs (AC voltage and current, torque and angular momentum, and DC current) are combined using an OR gate, such that if any of the inputs is faulty, the total output will be faulty.

However, after further analysis of the viability of this method, three main complications were identified. Firstly, manual labeling produced significantly different results from the original labeling produced by the virtual circuit (see section 4.3.1). Secondly, potential mislabeling could occur, particularly during

take-off and landing phases where the probability of values outside the range (3σ) is higher. Thirdly, due to the characteristics of the data, DC current, AC voltage, and angular momentum values mainly remain within 3 standard deviations, with only torque significantly defining the output. The resulting correlation matrix can be seen in Table B.34.

To further inspect the effect of the threshold method on data quality, the first 3 parameters, namely run number, time, and flight, were included in the correlation matrix. The resulting matrix showed a different range of values compared to the one obtained from the truth output as shown in Figure B.32. When using the threshold method, most values were on the scale of 10^{-2} , indicating a lower correlation between the variables. Thus, this approach could lead to a misleading analysis of error propagation within the ML models resulting from data corruption. This is because the threshold method can produce a more robust model compared to the truth output model obtained directly from the digital circuit. For the same amount of corrupted data, the threshold approach would have less impact, potentially neglecting certain impacts generated from corrupted data due to excessive model robustness.

4.3.3 20% Corrupted Output based on Truth Output

To balance the categorical output for ML without altering the data's characteristics, the group tested the 20% corrupted output. This involved changing 20% of the healthy class to the faulty class, resulting in an increase in the ratio of faulty to healthy classes from 5.33% to 31.78%, as shown in Figure B.35.

The confusion matrices in Figures B.36 and B.37 were created using the Fine Tree ML model on a total of 10 flightpaths. The training and testing sets were split in an 80:20 ratio. When using a 20% corrupted output to balance the categorical output, the accuracy of the training set decreased to 80.2%, and the accuracy of the testing set decreased to 80.4%.

In Figures B.38 and B.39, it is evident that the Fine Tree ML model did not perform well, as the AUC value was only 0.606. This indicates that the model was not able to capture the most important patterns in the data. One possible way to improve the ML performance would be to split the training and testing data into 70% and 30%, respectively. However, since a 20% corrupted output would be difficult to explain in the real world, this approach was not used.

4.3.4 5% Corrupted Output based on Truth Output

To minimize changes to the data while still making the ML challenging, another approach was explored. This approach defined the output as 5% corrupted by converting 5% of the healthy class in the truth output to faulty class. As shown in Figure 4.15, this resulted in an increase in the ratio of faulty to healthy classes from 5.33% to 10.98%.

Figure 4.15: Data Distribution of 5% Corrupted Output

The correlation matrix for the 5% corrupted output, as shown in Figure B.40, indicates that the majority of variables have a correlation coefficient in the range of 0.2 to 5% corrupted output. A comparison with Figure B.32 reveals that most correlation coefficients dropped from the range of 0.3 to 0.2, suggesting that the data characteristics have not changed significantly, unlike in the threshold method. Although the 5% corrupted output still provides a good response, it becomes challenging to predict accurately when ML input quality is corrupted by 5%.

Further investigation has been carried out on the three variables that are highly correlated with 5% corrupted output, namely DC current, AC current, and Angular momentum. Since the ENTHAN project focuses on the AC motor and inverter, the investigation has specifically focused on the implementation of transmission delay in M3.

Figure 4.16 and Figure 4.17 demonstrate that the AUC values for the validation set and test set are 0.7584 and 0.7587, respectively. These values indicate a significant improvement in performance compared to the AUC achieved using the 20% corrupted output method. As a result, the 5% corrupted output method was chosen as the benchmark for further ML investigations.

Figure 4.16: AUC of Validation set for 5% Corrupted Output

Figure 4.17: AUC of Test set for 5% Corrupted Output

4.4 ML with Uncorrupted Training

Therefore, this section presents graphs and conclusions in the context of the 5% corrupted output, which refers to the corruption in the digital circuit labelling column.

The relevance of time as an input variable to the ML model becomes important, and a brief analysis of its influence on the data characteristics has been carried out. Figure B.41 displays the resulting confusion matrix for the prediction of the Fine Tree model using two different transmission delay values. The data was corrupted for different values, with a delay of 200 samples and a delay of 400 samples, using the M1V1 method (see section 4.5.2). It can be observed that the data quality does not change significantly. Table 4.9 shows the specific number of different classifications for each area of the matrix.

Table 4.9: Number of different Classifications in the Confusion Matrix for the FT at 200 and 400 Samples per Row Delay, using the Transmission Delay Method M1V1

Confusion matrix parameter	Number of different classifications
True Positives	667
False Positives	667
False Negatives	867
True Negatives	867

Based on the results presented, it can be concluded that time sensitivity of the model has a marginal impact on the data characteristics. However, including time as an input variable creates a conflict with the implementation of transmission delay M2, which works with a continuous time frame. This is because the digital circuit defines samples from 0 seconds to 40 seconds for each flight path, resulting

in a repetition of the time range (0-40s) with a total of 10 repetitions. On the other hand, M2 uses a continuous time range of 0-400 seconds. Since time sensitivity of the model is negligible and M2 requires its own continuous time sample, time can be omitted as an input variable.

4.5 Corruption of Data Quality by Induced Error

This project explores two primary methods of corrupting data quality: reducing F_s and introducing transmission delay. In the case of transmission delay, three different methods were used, namely M1, M2, and M3. The investigation not only examines these methods individually but also explores combination cases, such as the implementation of transmission delay based on reduced F_s .

4.5.1 Reduce F_s

The data resolution reduction method used in this project is the MATLAB built-in function *downsample*. It involves deleting every Nth row of the dataset to achieve a lower resolution. For instance, if the original dataset has a F_s of 25 kHz and 10 million rows, using *downsample(data,2)* will result in a downsampled dataset with a F_s of 12.5 kHz and 5 million rows. The objective of this investigation is to determine the appropriate level of data resolution reduction that would still yield acceptable performance for the diagnostics performance.

4.5.2 Implementation of Transmission Delay

In this project, three different approaches are used to implement transmission delay. These approaches are:

- M1: Delete repetitive data within flightpath
- M2: Switch the order of the rows within flightpath
- M3: Delete a column of data from the beginning of flightpath

Each approach has a different impact on data quality, and the investigation aims to determine the acceptable level of transmission delay that can be tolerated without significantly impacting the diagnostics performance of the PHM system monitoring.

M1-V1

To introduce transmission delay, the MATLAB built-in function *delayseq* is used in this project. In Transmission delay M1 version 1, the entire input data is shifted down by a specified number of rows or seconds, while keeping the data size unchanged. For example, applying *delayseq(data,10,25e3)* to a dataset with 10 million rows and 18 columns would shift the data down for 10 seconds at a F_s of 25 kHz, resulting in the first 250,000 rows being filled with zeros. If *delayseq(data,10)* is used instead, the first 10 rows will be filled with zeros.

However, this method has a limitation: it introduces many zeros in the data, which can negatively affect ML performance and generate false results. As a result, an improved version of M1 has been developed.

Table 4.10: Difference between Reducing F_s at default and at specified F_s

Original Vector	M1V1	M1V1@25kHz
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0
4	0	0
5	0	0
6	0	0
7	0	0
8	0	0
9	0	0
10	0	0
11	1	0
12	2	0
13	3	0
14	4	0
15	5	0
16	6	0
17	7	0
18	8	0
19	9	0
20	10	0

Transmission Delay Method 1

The Transmission Delay M1 approach is an improved version of M1-V1 that uses NaN values instead of filling shifted rows with zeros. This approach ensures that any rows containing NaN are not taken into account by the ML algorithm, and the algorithm's performance is not affected. M1 and M3 iterate through 0s to 20s using 0.5s time increments, resulting in a total of 41 time steps.

It's important to note that this approach differs from reducing the F_s , which may also reduce the number of effective values recorded. For example, downsampling a column vector by a factor of 2 and then applying delayseq by 10 rows will result in a vector with the same number of recorded effective values, but a different size compared to the original vector.

As shown in table 4.11, transmission delay does not change the size of the vector and preserves the original order of recorded values when counting. However, reducing F_s deletes every other row because the downsample factor is 2.

One small limitation of this method is that if the actual value recorded is zero, it will be falsely marked as NaN. However, this case will be rare as it only occurs during changing flightpaths, and ML performance

might be abnormal during these times.

Table 4.11: Difference between Reducing F_s and M1

Original Vector	M1	Reduce Fs
1	NaN	1
2	NaN	3
3	NaN	5
4	NaN	7
5	NaN	9
6	NaN	11
7	NaN	13
8	NaN	15
9	NaN	17
10	NaN	19
11	1	
12	2	
13	3	
14	4	
15	5	
16	6	
17	7	
18	8	
19	9	
20	10	

Transmission Delay Method 2

A time shift is introduced into the simulated dataset to emulate the effects of jitter and variations in the arrival of data packets at the data logger. To ensure easy sorting by time later, the time values are set between 0 and 400s, as the input dataset goes from 0-40s ten times. A random vector of numbers between 0 and 1 is generated, and a percentage of rows in the dataset is selected to be affected by the time shift based on the values in this vector. Rows with values below the set percentage are selected, and they are shifted in time by a random value between 0 and a maximum time shift value. The time-shifted dataset is then sorted by time to simulate receiver and transmitter out-of-sync or latency. To ensure that there is no mislabelling between flights, the dataset is also sorted by flight number.

To evaluate the effect of the maximum transmission delay and the percentage of rows affected on the dataset, either the time or the percentage can be fixed, and the other variable is iterated over. A percentage of 10% is fixed when iterating over time, as empirical analysis showed this value had a significant impact on the data. Similarly, a time of 20s is fixed when iterating over the percentage, as the number of mislabelled rows was found to be stable at this point.

Figure 4.18 illustrates the time shift using M2 with some examples. The excerpt from the dataset shows a boundary region between the healthy state and the failed state, indicated by the label old column, which switches from mostly 0 to mostly 1 between time steps 27 and 28. As our input dataset was corrupted by 5%, some failures, indicated by 1, can be seen between time steps 1 and 27. Both the time between steps and the time offset are set to integers for easier comprehension.

The introduction of the time shift in M2 leads to mislabelling, as the comparison between the ML results and the labels is made against the old label instead of the updated label. The yellow and cyan colours illustrate a case of mislabelling, where the yellow row is selected to be moved to a different position, and both the old and new positions have the same label. However, the move leads to mislabelling because the row indicated by cyan is moved as well, even though it was not selected. The light and dark green colour pair indicates that the reverse can also be true when a selected row overtakes another selected row. A shift across the label boundary is indicated by the purple colour in 4.18, where a row is moved from the healthy part of the dataset into the faulty region of the dataset.

Label old	Time old	selected Rows	Timeshift 0-5	Time new	Label new	
0	1	0	0	0	1	0
0	2	0	0	0	2	0
0	3	0	0	0	3	0
0	4	0	0	0	4	0
0	5	0	0	0	5	0
0	6	0	0	0	6	0
0	7	1	3	8	0	
0	8	0	0	9	1	
1	9	0	0	10	0	
0	10	0	0	10	0	
0	11	0	0	11	0	
0	12	1	3	14	0	
0	13	1	1	14	0	
0	14	0	0	15	0	
1	15	1	5	16	0	
0	16	0	0	17	1	
0	17	0	0	18	0	
0	18	0	0	19	0	
1	19	0	0	20	0	
0	20	0	0	20	1	
0	21	0	0	21	0	
0	22	1	4	22	0	
0	23	0	0	23	0	
0	24	0	0	24	0	
0	25	0	0	25	0	
0	26	0	0	26	0	
0	27	1	3	27	1	
1	28	1	1	28	1	
1	29	0	0	29	1	
1	30	0	0	30	0	
1	31	0	0	31	1	
1	32	0	0	32	1	
1	33	0	0	33	1	
1	34	1	3	35	1	
1	35	0	0	36	1	
1	36	0	0	37	1	
1	37	0	0	37	1	
1	38	0	0	38	1	
1	39	0	0	39	1	
1	40	0	0	40	1	
1	41	0	0	41	1	
1	42	0	0	42	1	
1	43	0	0	43	1	

Figure 4.18: Method 2 Row Switching Methodology

Based on these observations, it can be concluded that most shifts result in two mislabelled rows. Additionally, it can be concluded that the majority of mislabelled rows are due to the five percent corruption introduced into the dataset in section 4.3.4, rather than the boundary layer swaps. Figure 4.19 displays plots of the percentage of mislabelled rows in a 25kHz dataset. These plots demonstrate that after a steep drop with a low maximum transmission delay, the percentage of mislabelled rows remains constant at around 13.8% with a maximum transmission delay of 200s. The lower plot provides a more detailed view of maximum transmission delays up to $\frac{50}{25000}$ s, which corresponds to up to 50 rows moved for selected rows. The flat spot at the beginning of the plot is explained by the fact that at this point, the maximum time shift is $\frac{1}{25000}$ s, which means that it is very unlikely that a selected row will be assigned the maximum time shift and moved further than its current position.

Figure 4.19: Plot of the number of Mislabeled Rows. Top: Up to 400s of maximum Transmission Delay. Middle: Up to $\frac{50}{25000}$ s of Maximum transmission delay. Bottom: Varying Percentage with a fixed Maximum Transmission Delay of 20s

Transmission Delay Method 3

The methodology for transmission delay M3 follows the same principle as M1, but with the difference that only a certain column, in this case AC current, is shifted down by a specified number of seconds at a given F_s , and then filled with NaN. AC current was chosen because it is highly correlated with the 5% corrupted output and also fits the ETHAN project better, where a DC voltage is connected to an inverter

and drives an AC motor. While DC current has the highest correlation to the 5% corrupted output, AC current is a better fit for the project's purpose.

In general, M3 works well for uncorrupted training cases. However, for corrupted training cases, a special case transmission delay, M3 80s with a 2.5kHz F_s , must be tailored to train ML models. This is because after reducing the F_s to 2.5kHz, there are 1 million rows of data in total, which is equivalent to a 40s single flight path. Since there is an 80s M3 transmission delay, the entire AC current column becomes NaN.

Combination Cases

This section presents the various combinations of data quality corruption that have been developed. The corrupting functions used are based on downsampling and transmission delay errors, as these errors can be attributed to physical phenomena such as jittering, and receiver and transmitter out of synchronization in real life. The sequence of applying these functions is important for optimizing computation time. First, the downsampling function is applied, and then the transmission delay function is applied to the obtained data.

Downsampling functions require less computation time than transmission delay functions, and hence, it makes sense to use downsampling methods to reduce the size of the dataset and save computation time for the transmission delay methods. This procedure results in a new dataset of reduced size, depending on the downsampling factor. The transmission delay functions do not change the size of the dataset and hence demand more computing capacity. By reducing the size of the dataset using downsampling and then inputting the data into a transmission delay function, computation time is saved.

Once the procedure is explained, the specific settings for the different functions are revealed. For the downsampling function, data reduction factors of 1, 2, 3, 6, 9, and 10 are selected. The selection of these factors is made for the following reasons: factor 1 provides a benchmark for comparing the performance of the model across the range of the rest of the factors; factor 10 is the maximum data reduction factor because going beyond this factor does not provide useful information in a physical context as the dataset has 10 repetitive flight paths; factors 2 and 3, and 9 and 10 are chosen with a spacing of factor 1 to conduct a more detailed analysis of the model's tendency in low and high data reduction factors, and to have a better overview of the values that are not represented; and factor 6 is chosen as the middle value, being equidistant from the previous and next values.

The transmission delay functions remain with a delay factor of 20 seconds. This is because a factor of 20 seconds corrupts half of the first dataset, and values above 20 seconds provide irrelevant information in a physical context. Finally, the resulting combination cases are shown in Figure 4.20.

Figure 4.20: Combination Cases Illustration

4.6 ML with Corrupted Training

So far in the project, a procedure has been presented for generating predictions on corrupted data using trained models and evaluating their performance. This involves training a ML algorithm on original data and then using the trained model to generate predictions for corrupted data. However, to conduct further analysis, it is essential to evaluate the performance of ML models using corrupted training data. This section presents various data corruption methodologies that are applied to an original dataset comprising 10 million rows and 18 columns, with a F_s of 25kHz. Providing this information helps in better understanding the methodology.

4.6.1 F_s at 2.5kHz

To reduce the F_s , this methodology involves using a built-in function that selects only one row for every ten rows in the original dataset when it runs from top to bottom. As a result, a new dataset with a reduced size of 1 million rows and 18 columns is generated, with a frequency of 2.5kHz. It is worth noting that this approach modifies the size of the original dataset. It is also interesting to analyze the performance of the ML models trained using this reduced dataset and then used to predict the full-frame data, i.e., 10 million rows and 18 columns.

4.6.2 20s M1 Transmission Delay

Methodology M1 also utilizes transmission delay as a means of data corruption. Specifically, a 20-second delay is introduced into the original dataset, resulting in corresponding rows being shifted down and empty slots being filled with NaN values. As a result, the corrupted dataset contains 0.5 million rows and 18 columns, with NaN values filling half of the first flight path in the original dataset, which consists

of 10 flight paths. The ML models are trained using this corrupted dataset and then used to predict the full-frame dataset, which contains 10 million rows and 18 columns.

4.6.3 F_s at 2.5kHz & 20s M1 Transmission Delay

Combination cases of data corruption are relevant in the context of physical systems, and it is important to create such scenarios. One such approach involves combining transmission delay and sample frequency reduction. To achieve this, the built-in function to reduce the sample frequency by a factor of 10 is first applied. Subsequently, the procedure from methodology M1 is applied, which introduces a delay of 20 seconds into the original dataset. The result is a corrupted dataset consisting of 0.5 million rows and 18 columns, with NaN values replacing the delayed data points. The frequency of this dataset is 2.5kHz. The ML models are trained using this dataset and then used to predict the full-frame data.

4.6.4 F_s at 2.5kHz & 80s M3 Transmission Delay at AC Current only

This combination case applies methodology M3, which is based on transmission delay. A delay factor of 80 seconds is used, affecting only the AC current column, as described in Section 5.1.4. At a frequency of 2.5kHz, all AC current column values become NaN. Therefore, special tailoring is necessary for training different ML models, as each model has different requirements for the input data.

The Fine Tree model requires no further modification, but the FT model does not consider the AC current column for the ML process. Therefore, the input data for the FT model includes only 13 variables, unlike other models that use 14 variables.

For the Narrow Neural Network model, the first row of AC current is changed to an extremely large number, such as 10000, and all the rest are set to NaN.

For the Naive Bayes model, the first 10 rows of AC current are set to extreme numbers such as 10000, and the last 10 rows are set to 1.

The limitation of using M3 for corrupted training is that cross-verification of the three different models is not possible as each model must be customized.

5 Data Analysis of different Corruption Methods on Diagnostics Performance

This chapter presents the result plots obtained from the FT model, which has shown the best overall performance. It should be noted that the data was not normalized, as discussed in section 2.4.3 and 2.4.3 which can have negative consequences. The plots obtained from the NB and NNN models can be found in the appendix for comparison.

5.1 ML with Uncorrupted Training

This section presents the results of experiments conducted to evaluate the effects of reducing F_s , transmission delay (M1, M2, and M3), and their combination on uncorrupted training.

5.1.1 Reducing F_s on the Model trained by Uncorrupted Data

Inspecting Figures C.1, C.2, and C.4 won't provide insight into data behavior due to the size reduction. Normalized accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 scores are fluctuating around 1, sometimes exceeding 1. Thus, these figures won't help gain insight into how reducing F_s affects data behavior or determine if further reduction improves performance, contradicting ML principles.

The original AUC for the Fine Tree (FT) model, Naive Bayes model (NB), and Narrow Neural Network (NNN) model are 0.7423, 0.6797, and 0.6011, respectively, with the FT model performing the best. From Figures 5.1, C.3, and C.5, the maximum allowable reduced F_s is 3, 3, and 4 times, respectively, for size reductions from 0-10. The maximum reduction factor is set at 10 because a similar dataset is repeated 10 times and used as ML input.

This indicates that, at the given 25 kHz data resolution, the maximum allowable reduction in matrix size is 8.333 kHz, as both the FT and NB models give the same result. The NNN model's result is excluded due to poor performance. However, AUC evaluations won't vary much since normalized AUC remains close to 1 (0.999 scale).

Figure 5.1: AUC of M1 DS 0-10 FT trained by Uncorrupted Data

5.1.2 Implement Transmission Delay M1 on the Model trained by Uncorrupted Data

The accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score of the FT, NB, and NNN models were evaluated for a 20-second M1 transmission delay. Figures C.16, C.20, and C.28 show that all evaluation metrics remain at high values, providing no useful information for the 0-20s M1 transmission delay range. However, at 10s, 8s, and 6s, the FT, NB, and NNN models respectively converged.

The original AUC values for the FT, NB, and NNN models are 0.7432, 0.6797, and 0.6011, respectively, indicating that the FT model has the best performance while the NNN model has the worst performance.

Looking at the normalized AUC figures, such as figure 5.2, figure C.8, and figure C.10, a normalized AUC of 0.7 indicates that the FT model indicates a time of 6.5 seconds, the NB model indicates 7 seconds, while the NNN model indicates that all normalized AUC values converge to 0.82 starting at 6 seconds. A higher original AUC value indicates better sensitivity, which is important for anomaly detection, especially when the data is denoised and without outliers.

Analyzing when the normalized AUC tends to converge shows that the FT model converges at 10 seconds, the NB model converges at 8 seconds, and the NNN model converges at 6 seconds. A well-performing model such as the FT model takes longer to converge since its performance on unseen data is better, while a poorly performing model such as the NNN model converges faster due to its under-fitting to a sub-optimal solution.

Since the FT model has demonstrated the best performance, the maximum allowable data corruption is 1.625% (6.5s/400s) of the entire dataset to achieve a normalized AUC of 0.7. If model performance

is not a top priority, the maximum allowable transmission delay for M1 could be increased to 2.5% (10s/400s) of the entire dataset.

In general, when the correlation coefficient between the ML output and the data falls within the scale of 0.2 and the data size is in the scale of 10 million, a maximum M1 transmission delay of a 0-20s in the range of 1.625% to 2.5% of the entire data package is allowed without significantly affecting performance.

In the combination case, as shown in figure 5.3, figure C.13, and figure C.15, reducing the F_s has little effect on the M1 transmission delay, and only the FT model showed a subtle difference. The FT, NB, and NNN models tend to converge at their respective M1 transmission delays of 10s, 8s, and 6s. However, taking a closer look at the FT model, it has a higher AUC value at 4.167 kHz than at 8.333 kHz, which has no physical explanation in the real world. Thus, it can be concluded that, in the combination case, the maximum allowable corruption is 4s at 8.333 kHz, meaning that the maximum M1 transmission delay is 1% of the entire data at 33.3% of its original data size.

Figure 5.2: AUC of M1 TD 0-20s FT trained by Uncorrupted Data

Figure 5.3: AUC of Combination of DS and M1 TD 0-20s FT trained by Uncorrupted Data

5.1.3 Implement Transmission Delay M2 on the Model trained by Uncorrupted Data

Introducing a 20-second transmission delay for M2 caused all ML models (FT, NB, and NNN) to fail to converge within the given time window. This is evident from Figures 5.4, C.37, and C.38, which show that the models' original AUC values were 0.74229, 0.67974, and 0.6011, respectively. Despite the models' performance being in the desired range, the M2 transmission delay failed to converge due to insufficient row switching in the time window. However, Figure C.36 shows that M2 transmission delay tended to converge after 300 seconds within a time window of 400 seconds, indicating that the delay had little impact on diagnostic performance.

Combining M2 with reduced F_s has little impact on data quality, as shown by the six different reduced frequencies in Figures 5.6, C.41, and C.42, which overlap. Additionally, the normalized AUC values remain close to 1, indicating that the diagnostic performance was not affected by the reduced quality of the data.

The FT model exhibits a steeper drop in normalized AUC compared to the NB model, which appears to tolerate the M2 transmission delay of 0-3 seconds more effectively. This is likely due to the characteristics of the NB model, which assumes that inputs are independent of each other, resulting in suboptimal predictions for inputs with highly correlated features. Additionally, the NB algorithm is simple, resulting in more stable and consistent AUC values across different test sets.

In contrast, the FT model exhibits a high negative gradient due to its ability to respond well to increasing M2 transmission delays, but it is not able to converge due to the highly imbalanced nature of the dataset.

As a result, the algorithm may have difficulty accurately predicting the minority class, which can lead to a rapid drop in the AUC value.

Figure 5.5 shows that the maximum tolerance is 28% for randomly selected data with a 20-second M2 transmission delay. The reason for the higher tolerance compared to M1 is that M2 transmission only changes the sequence of the data packages by randomly shifting down the selected rows within a range of 0 to 0.5 million rows (i.e., 20 seconds).

On the other hand, both the NB and NNN models tend to have the first lowest AUC value at a relatively lower tolerance compared to the FT model, as shown in Figures C.39 and C.40. This is due to the poor performance of the NB and NNN models, which are not able to accurately differentiate between the positive and negative samples, resulting in a low AUC value. However, the high percentage allowance makes it difficult to accurately reflect the real world, and further investigation on varying the percentage at a fixed 20s M2 transmission delay is necessary.

Figure 5.4: AUC of M2 0-20S TD FT trained by Uncorrupted Data

Figure 5.5: AUC of M2 TD 0-20S FT and a varying Percentage made with M2 trained by Uncorrupted Data

Figure 5.6: AUC of FT with M2 TD 0-20S and DS 1-10 trained by Uncorrupted Data

5.1.4 Implement Transmission Delay M3 on the Model trained by Uncorrupted Data

This section examines the effects of M3 transmission delay on model performance, both individually and in combination with reduced F_s .

When a 20-second transmission delay was introduced in M3, the original AUCs for the FT, NB, and NNN models were 0.7423, 0.6797, and 0.6011, respectively. The FT model performed the best with M3 transmission delay. To determine the maximum tolerance of the model, the first occurrence of the lowest

point in AUC was chosen, as this is unlikely to happen in real-life scenarios. The results show that the maximum tolerance of M3 transmission delay for the FT model is at 2.5s, which represents 0.625% of its original data. In contrast, the NB and NNN models exhibited a direct decrease and did not converge to a certain value at the given 0-20s transmission delay. These models were not sensitive enough to detect the subtle changes in transmission delay and were not considered for further evaluation.

In the combination case, the FT model also indicated a maximum tolerance at 2.5s, which represents 0.625% of its original data. The size reduction had little effect on M3 transmission delay as they were all overlapping. However, the NB and NNN models were not sensitive to M3 transmission delay, and it was difficult to draw any conclusion from their performance. In general, it can be concluded that the maximum tolerance for M3 transmission delay is 0.625% of its original data.

Figure 5.7: AUC of Combination of DS and M3 TD 0-20s FT trained by Uncorrupted Data

5.2 ML with Corrupted Training

This section presents the results of experiments conducted to evaluate the effects of reducing F_s , transmission delay (M1, M2, and M3), and their combination on corrupted training.

5.2.1 Implement Transmission Delay M1 on the Model trained by Corrupted Data

The FT, NB, and NNN ML models were trained using four corrupted cases: reduced F_s at 2.5 kHz (Case 1), M1 transmission delay of 20 seconds (Case 2), a combination of 20 seconds M1 transmission delay at 2.5 kHz (Case 3), and a combination of 80 seconds M3 transmission delay at 2.5 kHz (Case 4).

The **FT model**'s original AUC for these four different cases were 0.7110, 0.7494, 0.7199, and 0.7348, respectively. Figures 5.9, 5.8, 5.10, and 5.11 show that all FT models tend to converge at 10 seconds. To achieve a normalized AUC larger than 0.7, the maximum allowable M1 transmission delay is 9 seconds, 9 seconds, 9 seconds, and 8 seconds, respectively. In general, the M1 transmission delay is allowed to be in the range of 8 to 10 seconds, which represents 2% to 2.5% of its original data.

The **NB model**'s original AUC for the four different corrupted cases were 0.6780, 0.6918, 0.6971, and 0.5358, respectively. Figures C.21, C.23, C.25, and C.27 show that the model tends to converge at 8s, 10s, 8s, and 8s, respectively. If the model achieves a normalized AUC larger than 0.7, it will converge at 7.5s, 7.8s, 4.8s, and not applicable for the four different cases, respectively. The M1 transmission delay is allowed to be in the range of 4.8s to 7.8s, representing 1.2% to 1.95% of the original data.

The **NNN model**'s original AUC values for the four different cases were 0.6545, 0.5737, 0.6734, and 0.5, respectively. The 80s transmission delay at 2.5kHz has the worst performance, as its normalized AUC remains at 1. Figures C.29, C.31, C.33, and C.27 show that the model is converging at 9.6s, 4.8s, 14s, and not happening, respectively. The lowest point for all four cases occurs at 4.8s, 6s, 6s, and not happening. In general, the M1 transmission delay is allowed to be in the range of 4.8s to 6s, representing 1.2% to 1.5% of its original data. This lowest point indicates that the model was not able to capture the pattern of the data and therefore cannot produce meaningful ML information.

Figure 5.8: AUC of Combination of DS and M1 TD 0-20s FT trained by Corrupted Data Case 1

Figure 5.9: AUC of Combination of DS and M1 TD 0-20s FT trained by Corrupted Data Case 2

Figure 5.10: AUC of Combination of DS and M1 TD 0-20s FT trained by Corrupted Data Case 3

Figure 5.11: AUC of Combination of DS and M1 TD 0-20s FT trained by Corrupted Data Case 4

5.2.2 Implement Transmission Delay M2 on the Model trained by Corrupted Data

In this section, three ML models (FT, NB, and NNN) were trained using four different corrupted cases: reduced F_s at 2.5 kHz (Case 1), M1 transmission delay of 20 seconds (Case 2), a combination of 20 seconds M1 transmission delay at 2.5 kHz (Case 3), and a combination of 80 seconds M3 transmission delay at 2.5 kHz (Case 4).

The original AUC values of the **FT model** for these four cases were 0.74938, 0.71104, 0.71994, and 0.731, respectively. However, all versions of the FT model failed to converge within the given time window and exhibited a persistent negative gradient, as illustrated in Figure 5.12, Figure 5.13, Figure 5.14, and Figure 5.15.

On the other hand, the **NB model** and **NNN model** maintained the general shape of the uncorrupted training case, with the exception of one case shown in Figure C.48. In this case, the NB model's normalized AUC tended to be higher than 1 because the AUC value of 0.53578 corresponded to random classification, where the majority class (class 0 as Healthy) was returned due to data imbalance. Therefore, the increase in normalized AUC was reasonable. Additionally, in Figure C.44, the normalized AUC remained at 1, which was explained by the same reason mentioned above.

Figure 5.12: AUC of Combination of DS and M2 TD 0-20s FT trained by Corrupted Data Case 1

Figure 5.13: AUC of Combination of DS and M2 TD 0-20s FT trained by Corrupted Data Case 2

Figure 5.14: AUC of Combination of DS and M2 TD 0-20s FT trained by Corrupted Data Case 3

Figure 5.15: AUC of Combination of DS and M2 TD 0-20s FT trained by Corrupted Data Case 4

5.2.3 Implement Transmission Delay M3 on the Model trained by Corrupted Data

In this section, three ML models (FT, NB, and NNN) were trained on four corrupted datasets, which included reduced F_s at 2.5 kHz (Case 1), M1 transmission delay of 20 seconds (Case 2), a combination of 20 seconds M1 transmission delay at 2.5 kHz (Case 3), and a combination of 80 seconds M3 transmission delay at 2.5 kHz (Case 4).

The **FT model** achieved an original AUC of 0.7110, 0.7494, 0.7199, and 0.7348 for the four cases, respectively. Figures 5.17, 5.16, 5.18, and 5.19 show that the maximum tolerance is at 2.5s, 3s, 3s, and not occurring, respectively. The ML model's performance in predicting M3 transmission delay significantly degraded when trained on the corrupted 20s transmission delay dataset, as the AUC value

converges faster than the others. This indicates that using a corrupted training model makes it difficult to predict the full-frame data due to a lack of diversity in the training data.

The **NB model** achieved an original AUC of 0.6789, 0.6918, 0.6971, and 0.5630 for the four cases, respectively. Figures C.67, C.69, C.71, and C.73 show that the maximum tolerance values are not occurring. The extreme case is the 80s transmission delay at 2.5kHz, and the normalized AUC increases as more M3 corruption is introduced. This is because of the model's poor performance, and as long as the ML predicts the 0 class, it is likely to be correct due to the data imbalance, as discussed in section 4.3.4.

The **NNN model** achieved an original AUC of 0.6545, 0.5737, 0.6734, and 0.5 for the four cases, respectively, indicating poor performance. Due to its poor performance, the NNN model was not able to use the corrupted training set to predict the full-frame data.

Figure 5.16: AUC of Combination of DS and M3 TD 0-20s FT trained by Corrupted Data Case 1

Figure 5.17: AUC of Combination of DS and M3 TD 0-20s FT trained by Corrupted Data Case 2

Figure 5.18: AUC of Combination of DS and M3 TD 0-20s FT trained by Corrupted Data Case 3

Figure 5.19: AUC of Combination of DS and M3 TD 0-20s FT trained by Corrupted Data Case 4

6 Evaluation

This chapter provides a summary of the project's requirements, achievements, data characteristics, summary of data quality corruption, and final conclusion.

6.1 Verification and Validation of Project Requirements

This section analyzes the success of the project's steps using a scheme for cross-verifying the process and results (Figure A.7). The generated dataset from the digital circuit successfully accomplishes the design requirements (DR 1) with a F_s of 25 kHz, 18 variables, and non-Gaussian noise. The use of sensors has also been implemented for anomaly detection, allowing for observation of the impact of such anomalies on dataset quality and categorization of healthy and faulty states (categorical output) (DR 2). The requirements for data manipulation (DR 3) have been accomplished with the sensible data to malfunctioning and categorical output. However, the FR 8 of achieving a normalized accuracy of 70% by corrupting the data was not fulfilled for all three models due to their lack of generalization, as only the FT model converged within the given time window. Despite this, it does not affect the fact that DR4 has been achieved.

The project achieved Level 3 from the defined levels of success (Figure A.6). The final dataset contains non-Gaussian noise and randomised flightpaths based on a non-Gaussian distribution. Three ML models were successfully implemented to generate predictions, and a manual labelling approach was used to determine the output (i.e., goal). The dataset was originated from physically meaningful sensors, and 41 step bins were used to analyze error propagation for M1 and M3, while six step bins were used for the size reduction method. The evaluation section analyzed particular and combined error cases, studying the achieved precision, recall, F1 score, and AUC of the diagnostic performance.

6.2 Overview of the Data Characteristics

The project's data consists of 10 different datasets, each with the same structure and organization. Each dataset corresponds to a different run (total of 10 runs). This amount of runs strikes a good balance between computational requirements and model complexity. The available computational support for this project means that data manipulation operations would take a long time or require more powerful resources. However, the data cannot be too reduced since the predictability of such data would be too easy for the ML algorithm, rendering the conclusions unusable for the project's scope.

Regarding the structure of the individual datasets, they consist of 18 variables, forming the 18 columns. Figure 6.1 provides an overview of these variables. The matrix comprises 17 variables and the label column (the goal), which has a 5% corruption (section 4.3.4). Not all variables are relevant as inputs

to the ML algorithms. Specifically, the first three variables are dismissed because they provide no relevant information related to classifying the system as healthy or faulty. The run number indicates the numeration of each dataset from 0 to 10 and does not correlate with determining the state of the system itself. In fact, it could negatively impact the ML algorithms' predictions by misleading them to a nonexistent relationship between the run number and the healthy/faulty state. The time variable counts the time at which a sensor from the circuit provides data. It ranges from 0 to 40 seconds for each run and is a conflicting parameter when using the M2 transmission delay approach (section 4.4), which is why it is not used as an input. The flight variable describes the flight state and takes values 1, 2, and 3, corresponding to taking-off, cruise mode, and landing, respectively. Therefore, it should not correlate with the actual state of the system. Furthermore, since the scope of the project focuses on the data mining hardware side, the flight state does not represent a real measure of the system and is not relevant. However, one possible limitation is that a complex relationship between the likelihood of having a failure during a certain stage of the flightpath might exist, which would be missed in this case. Incorporating a variable that provides complex information could add extra difficulty and compromise the interpretation of the results. Also, since the data obtained from the digital circuit has an artificial origin, such a complex correlation might be even more challenging to associate with physical meaning, leading to an unnecessarily tedious process.

In summary, comparing back to the design requirements (see section 3.2) and the functional requirements (see figure A.4), it can be shown that the resulting dataset meets the expected characteristics. The expected dataset would be based on a high-frequency electric signal (around 20kHz), contain at least four variables, non-Gaussian noise, and constitute a large amount of data. The created dataset has a sampling rate frequency of 25kHz, contains 18 variables, and includes a total of 10 million data samples to which a non-Gaussian noise filter has been successfully applied.

Var 1	Var 2	Var 3	Var 4	Var 5	Var 6	Var 7	Var 8	Var 9	Var 10	Var 11	Var 12	Var 13	Var 14	Var 15	Var 16	Var 17	Var 18
Run Number	Time	Flight	DC Voltage	DC Current	DC Resistance	AC Volatge	AC Current	Motor Angle	Motor Angular Velocity	Torque	Temperature Stator A	Temperature Stator B	Temperature Stator C	Temperature Rotor	Power	Angular Momentum	Goal
...
⋮ 10 ⁶ rows																	

Figure 6.1: ML variables

Figure 6.2: Correlation Coefficients to Corrupted Output with 5% Labeling Corruption

In all of the different transmission delay methods - M1, M2, and M3 - transmission delay times are taken from 0-20s, which is a realistic timeframe in the real world. For example, if there are 10 vertically concatenated flight paths, each lasting for 40s, a 20s transmission delay would be an extreme case as the first half of the first flight path is filled with NaN (i.e., M1).

However, the data science side inspected an extreme case rather than a realistic one. As shown in Figure 6.3, there was a 100-second M1 transmission delay, resulting in 25% of the data being filled with NaN. Assuming the minimum accepted normalized AUC is 0.7, it shows that the AUC dropped as the number of NaN values increased (i.e., increased transmission delay) and it started to converge after a 10s transmission delay. However, the normalized AUC bounced back and peaked at 40s and 80s when the flight path changed from RUN 1 to RUN 2 and from RUN 2 to RUN 3. As mentioned earlier in Section 4.5.2, during the take-off and landing phase, where the actual recorded value is zero, it will be falsely marked as NaN, resulting in the ML models failing to capture the correct information and patterns.

To avoid this situation, a 20s transmission delay was used as there was no alteration in the flight path during this time window, unlike during the initial take-off phase.

Figure 6.3: Fine Tree M1 Transmission Delay from 0-100s with time increment 0.5s

6.3 Summary of Reducing F_s

In general, it can be concluded that reducing the F_s has little effect on data performance under the condition that ML accuracy is not the top priority, due to the repetitiveness of the data. However, if a dataset has the same characteristics as in this project, it is safe to say that reducing the F_s by a factor of 1-3 is acceptable, meaning a 1/3 in its original data size will represent the data well enough. Further conclusions will depend on the specific combination of factors involved.

6.4 Summary of M1

The FT model outperformed the NB and NNN models in predicting M1 transmission delay. Thus, it can be concluded that M1 transmission delay is tolerable as long as it is less than or equal to 2.5% of its original data, which represents 33.3% of the total data.

6.5 Summary of M2

In summary, the FT model has the best performance in predicting M2 transmission delay, indicating that M2 will not have a negative impact on diagnostic performance. This is because M2 introduces high randomness in both the percentage of packages selected and the transmission time window over a span of 10 million data. Since M2 does not introduce any human-made or systematic errors to the data, the

entity of the data remains the same, with the only difference being the sequence of rows that were changed.

6.6 Summary of M3

The FT model outperforms the other models in handling M3 transmission delay. However, when trained on corrupted data, all models perform poorly. This is because M3 loses information from the AC current column, and with too much unseen data in the training set and ML input, the model loses too much useful information. When using an uncorrupted training set, the maximum tolerance for M3 transmission delay is 0.625% of its original data, which represents one-third of the total data. The impact of size reduction on M3 is negligible, similar to M1 transmission delay.

6.7 Summary of difference between Uncorrupted and Corrupted Training for M1

Table 6.1 demonstrates a comparison of the performance of M1 TD on corrupted and uncorrupted training data. The lower threshold increased from 1.625% to 2%, while the upper limit remained at 2.5%. This adjustment is reasonable due to the presence of corruption in the training data, which required a higher minimum tolerance to compensate for the imperfections in the model.

Moreover, Table 6.1 indicates that M2 did not converge within the given time window, whereas M3 demonstrated negligible changes, as it is unable to converge in the worst-case scenario (i.e., Case 4).

Table 6.1: Summary of TD trained on different Cases

Fine Tree Model	M1	M2	M3
Uncorrupted	1.625%(6.5s) – 2.5%(10s)	Not converging between 0-20s	0.625%(2.5 s)
Corrupted Case 1	2.25%(9 s) – 2.5%(10 s)	Not converging between 0-20s	0.625%(2.5 s)
Corrupted Case 2	2.25%(9 s) – 2.5%(10 s)	Not converging between 0-20s	0.75%(3 s)
Corrupted Case 3	2.25%(9s) – 2.5%(10s)	Not converging between 0-20s	0.75%(3s)
Corrupted Case 4	2%(8s) – 2.5%(10s)	Not converging between 0-20s	Not converging between 0-20s

Since M1 is the only TD that displays a slight difference between uncorrupted and corrupted training, it is interesting to compare all cases of M1 in a single diagram (Figure 6.4) and investigate the difference. Regardless of the trained model used for M1, all of them converge within 10 seconds (i.e., 2.5% of the entire data). However, the time they reach their lowest acceptance varies. Corrupted cases 2, 3, and 4 tend to perform better than the original case (i.e., maximum tolerance is increased), likely due to the level of the most corrupted model: $Case4 > Case3 > Case2 > Case1$. However, since there are many unseen data for cases 2, 3, and 4, their models do not perform well, as the normalized AUC was low, indicating that these models were not sensitive enough to detect anomalies (i.e., prolonged maximum tolerance).

Overall, the impact on diagnostic performance is negligible when training with either uncorrupted or corrupted data.

Figure 6.4: AUC of differential M1 TD trained on different data

6.8 Conclusion

The data used in this project is highly continuous and repetitive, with data loggers measuring 40 seconds of flight path data over a 1 million data span for each individual flight path. The total data includes 10 flight paths that are similar to each other, with the only difference being the randomness, as shown in Figure 4.3. The data is highly imbalanced, with the majority being class 0 (Healthy) and the minority (Faulty) being class 1, and the correlation of each data logger is around 0.2 to the ML output.

In general, conclusions can be drawn from datasets that are similar to the one used in this project. Since the FT model has the best performance overall, all following conclusions are mainly based on the FT model.

The different transmission delay approaches have different impacts on diagnostics performance, and they are ranked as $M3 > M1 > M2$. M3 corrupts and deletes an AC Current column, which is a feature of the ML input. M1 corrupts and deletes relative information that is repeated 10 times in the data. M2 does not introduce extreme values or delete any relevant data information, and therefore, the data entity remains the same. M2 involves randomly selecting a fixed percentage or a fixed maximum transmission range for row switching.

For the method of adding NaN from top to bottom sequence (i.e., M1), the maximum tolerance for transmission delay is in the range of 1.625% to 2.5% (i.e., 6.5s to 10s in 400s data) of the entire

package. With the combination of reducing the sampling frequency F_s , the maximum tolerance for M1 transmission delay with 1/3 of the original dataset is 1% (i.e., 4s at 8.33kHz). Uncorrupted and corrupted training will not make a huge difference in the maximum tolerance, which is at 2.5% of the whole data, but the lower bound increases to 2% when it is trained with corrupted data, and it is not sensitive enough to capture the full-frame data's information. In short, as long as the M1 transmission delay is under 2.5% of 1/3 of the whole data, it will make the diagnostic performance reach the desired level.

For the method of row switching (i.e., M2), it has little impact on the data quality, as the entity of the data remains the same. Thus, the tolerance is higher at 28% of 1/3 of the whole data.

For the method of corrupting columns (i.e., M3), the maximum tolerance for transmission delay is 2.5s, representing 0.625% of 1/3 of the original data.

In conclusion, it is safe to say that the maximum tolerated transmission delay for all the methods implemented in this project is 0.625% of 1/3 of the original data, subject to the discussed constraints. Interrupting the data entity by introducing errors or extreme values has a greater impact on diagnostics performance than making internal changes (M2, i.e., row switches). The use of F_s deletes data details, such as repetitiveness and rows, has minimal impact. Both M2 and reducing F_s interrupt the data sequence, but their impact is negligible ($M3 > M1 > M2 > F_s$). In general, the data sequence is the least important factor affecting diagnostics performance, provided that the data entity remains unchanged. Those specifications for data quality can be utilized to determine the design requirements for the onboard data logger measurement hardware in the ETHAN framework.

7 Further Improvement

This chapter presents the limitations of this project and offers suggestions for further improvements for future use.

7.1 Implementing Weighted Algorithm

One limitation of this project is the imbalanced nature of the data, which may impact the performance of the ML models. To address this, a weighted algorithm must be implemented to ensure a proportional split of the two classes, namely Healthy and Faulty, with a target split of 80% vs. 20%. This can be achieved through a stratified split using a weighted algorithm to ensure that both the training and testing sets contain a proportional split of the two classes. Currently, the ratio of Faulty to Healthy class samples is 10.98%, which is significantly imbalanced. By implementing a weighted algorithm, the ML models can be trained on a balanced dataset, which may improve their performance in diagnosing faults in the aircraft system.

7.2 Different Approach of Reducing Resolution

In this project, only reducing the number of rows has been tested as a method of reducing resolution. However, it would be interesting to explore the impact of reducing the number of columns on the ML model's performance. The comparison of transmission delays M1 and M3 revealed that omitting the AC current column had a greater impact on data quality than omitting 90% of the rows. This is because, in real-life scenarios, when a sensor stops working, it no longer provides any data to the PHM matrix, resulting in a significant increase in the amount of unseen data. Therefore, low-resolution data tends to be more corrupted. It would be useful to determine how much tolerance the data has after certain columns are corrupted or deleted.

7.3 Frequency-Domain Analysis

To clarify, the simulated data used in this project only describes the object (AC Motor) in a static state and does not include any vibration state such as vibrations in the system that can be measured. As a result, the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) could not be applied to the data. However, all data corruption methods were implemented in the time domain. It would be interesting to investigate the data's tolerance to transmission delays in the frequency domain, as there are additional factors to consider in this domain, such as aliasing.

Bibliography

- [1] 2019 3rd International Conference on Electronic Information Technology and Computer Engineering (EITCE). IEEE, 2019. ISBN: 978-1-7281-3584-7.
- [2] Oludare Isaac Abiodun et al. “State-of-the-art in artificial neural network applications: A survey”. In: *Heliyon* 4.11 (2018), e00938. ISSN: 2405-8440. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405844018332067>.
- [3] Juan Acostupa. *Condition Monitoring of Hydraulic Systems*. 25.08.2019. URL: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/jjacostupa/condition-monitoring-of-hydraulic-systems?select=description.txt>.
- [4] Rosmaini Ahmad and Shahrul Kamaruddin. “An overview of time-based and condition-based maintenance in industrial application”. In: *Computers & Industrial Engineering* 63.1 (2012), pp. 135–149. ISSN: 0360-8352. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360835212000484>.
- [5] Analog Devices. *Low-Pass Filter: What is a Low-Pass Filter?* URL: <https://www.analog.com/en/design-center/glossary/low-pass-filter.html>.
- [6] arnab. *Microsoft Azure Predictive Maintenance*. 15.10.2020. URL: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/arnabbiswas1/microsoft-azure-predictive-maintenance>.
- [7] B. C. Pai and S. S. Ram. “Impact of normalization and standardization on neural network classification of colorectal cancer”. In: *Journal of Medical Systems* 41 (2017), pp. 1–10.
- [8] B². *NASA Turbofan Jet Engine Data Set*. 26.07.2019. URL: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/behrad3d/nasa-cmaps>.
- [9] Ernie Illyani Basri et al. “Preventive maintenance (PM) planning: a review”. In: *Journal of Quality in Maintenance Engineering* 23.2 (2017), pp. 114–143. ISSN: 1355-2511. URL: <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/JQME-04-2016-0014/full/pdf>.
- [10] Abdul Bin Bon et al., eds. *Proceedings of the Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Management, Business, Applied Science, Engineering and Sustainability Development, ICMASES 2019, 9-10 February 2019, Malang, Indonesia*. EAI, 2020. ISBN: 978-1-63190-217-8.
- [11] C. M. Bishop. *Pattern recognition and machine learning*. New York: Springer, 2006.
- [12] brjapon. *Gearbox Fault Diagnosis*. 23.02.2021. URL: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/brjapon/gearbox-fault-diagnosis>.
- [13] Ana Cachada et al. “Maintenance 4.0: Intelligent and Predictive Maintenance System Architecture”. In: *2018 IEEE 23rd International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (ETFA)*. Piscataway, NJ: IEEE, 2018, pp. 139–146. ISBN: 978-1-5386-7108-5.
- [14] Francesca Calabrese et al. “Predictive Maintenance: A Novel Framework for a Data-Driven, Semi-Supervised, and Partially Online Prognostic Health Management Application in Industries”. In: *Applied Sciences* 11.8 (2021), p. 3380.

-
- [15] Thyago P. Carvalho et al. "A systematic literature review of machine learning methods applied to predictive maintenance". In: *Computers & Industrial Engineering* 137 (2019), p. 106024. ISSN: 0360-8352. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360835219304838>.
- [16] *Controlling Random Number Generation - MATLAB & Simulink Example - MathWorks Deutschland*. 2.04.2023. URL: <https://de.mathworks.com/help/matlab/math/controlling-random-number-generation.html>.
- [17] P. Domingos. *A few useful things to know about machine learning: Communications of the ACM*. 2012.
- [18] Douw Marx, PS Heyns, and Stephan Schmidt. *Towards a hybrid approach for diagnostics and prognostics of planetary gearboxes*. 2021.
- [19] electronics-club. *Transmission Errors*. Ed. by electronics-club. URL: <https://electronics-club.com/transmission-errors/>.
- [20] elprocus. *What is a High Pass Filter? Circuit Diagram, Characteristics, and Applications*. URL: <https://www.elprocus.com/what-is-a-high-pass-filter-circuit-diagram-characteristics-and-applications/>.
- [21] *Error Detection & Correction*. 1.04.2023. URL: https://www.tutorialspoint.com/computer_logical_organization/error_codes.htm.
- [22] *eVTOL Battery Dataset*. 2021. URL: https://kilthub.cmu.edu/articles/dataset/eVTOL_Battery_Dataset/14226830?file=26855066.
- [23] Felipe M. L. Ribeiro. *MAFAULDA*. URL: https://www02.smt.ufrj.br/~offshore/mfs/page_01.html.
- [24] Flavio Trojan. "Classification to Clarify Maintenance Concepts in Production and Operations Management". In: *Journal of Business Economics* (2017). URL: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Flavio-Trojan/publication/324823247_Proposal_of_Maintenance-types_Classification_to_Clarify_Maintenance_Concepts_in_Production_and_Operations_Management/links/5ae479efaca272ba507effdc/Proposal-of-Maintenance-types-Classification-to-Clarify-Maintenance-Concepts-in-Production-and-Operations-Management.pdf.
- [25] H. Greeff et al. *Condition Monitoring for Handpumps - vibration data*. 2018.
- [26] Han, J., Ding, H., Jiang, Z., & Liao, W. "A Real-time Monitoring System for Bridge Safety Based on Structural Health Monitoring and Internet of Things". In: *2016 IEEE International Conference on Prognostics and Health Management* (2016), pp. 1–6.
- [27] H. M. Hashemian. "State-of-the-Art Predictive Maintenance Techniques". In: *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement* 60.1 (2011), pp. 226–236. ISSN: 0018-9456.
- [28] Haibo He and E. A. Garcia. "Learning from Imbalanced Data". In: *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* 21.9 (2009), pp. 1263–1284. ISSN: 1041-4347.
- [29] Li-Yu Hu et al. "The distance function effect on k-nearest neighbor classification for medical datasets". In: *SpringerPlus* 5.1 (2016), p. 1304. ISSN: 2193-1801.
- [30] Hu et al. "Prognostics and health management: A review of the current status, remaining challenges, and future developments in manufacturing and process industries". In: *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics* 68 (Jan. 2021), pp. 28–43.

-
- [31] Huan Huang. *Bearing Vibration Data under Time-varying Rotational Speed Conditions*. 2018.
- [32] Iberdrola. *Predictive maintenance: the key data-driven technique for anticipating errors*. 30.03.2023. URL: <https://www.iberdrola.com/innovation/predictive-maintenance>.
- [33] *IBM Documentation*. 2021. URL: <https://www.ibm.com/docs/en/spss-modeler/saas?topic=models-how-svm-works>.
- [34] *IBM Documentation*. 2021. URL: <https://www.ibm.com/docs/en/spss-modeler/saas?topic=models-how-svm-works>.
- [35] Jack Bonatakis, Abbas Chokor, Nicholas Propes. *PHM Data Challenge*. 2017. URL: <https://phmsociety.org/conference/annual-conference-of-the-phm-society/annual-conference-of-the-prognostics-and-health-management-society-2018-b/phm-data-challenge-6/>.
- [36] Jasper Kyle Catapang. *k-Nearest Neighbor Optimization via Randomized Hyperstructure Convex Hull*. Ed. by University of the Philippines Manila. 2016. URL: <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1906/1906.04559.pdf>.
- [37] Jim Frost. *Guidelines for Removing and Handling Outliers in Data*. URL: <https://statisticsbyjim.com/basics/remove-outliers/>.
- [38] Kai Goebel. *Gearbox Fault Detection Dataset, PHM Data Challenge 2009*. 2017.
- [39] Ziqiu Kang, Cagatay Catal, and Bedir Tekinerdogan. “Remaining Useful Life (RUL) Prediction of Equipment in Production Lines Using Artificial Neural Networks”. In: *Sensors (Basel, Switzerland)* 21.3 (2021).
- [40] Jack Kelly and William Knottenbelt. “The UK-DALE dataset, domestic appliance-level electricity demand and whole-house demand from five UK homes”. In: *Scientific data* 2 (2015), p. 150007. ISSN: 2052-4463.
- [41] Nam-Ho Kim, Dawn An, and Joo-Ho Choi. *Prognostics and Health Management of Engineering Systems*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2017. ISBN: 978-3-319-44740-7.
- [42] KirgSn. *Electric Motor Temperature*. 26.04.2021. URL: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/wkirgSn/electric-motor-temperature>.
- [43] Jaideep Reddy Kotla. *Power Quality Classification Dataset - 1*. 4.04.2021. URL: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/jaideepreddykotla/powerqualitydistributiondataset1>.
- [44] Kuhn, M., & Johnson, K. “Applied Predictive Modeling”. In: (2013), p. 86.
- [45] L. Szymanski and B. McCane. “Deep, super-narrow neural network is a universal classifier”. In: *The 2012 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*. 2012, pp. 1–8. ISBN: 2161-4407.
- [46] L. Yu, H. Liu, and H. Liu. “Efficient feature selection via analysis of relevance and redundancy”. In: *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 5 (2004), pp. 1205–1224.
- [47] Joffrey L. Leevy et al. “A survey on addressing high-class imbalance in big data”. In: *Journal of Big Data* 5.1 (2018), pp. 1–30. ISSN: 2196-1115. URL: <https://journalofbigdata.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40537-018-0151-6>.
- [48] Yaguo Lei et al. “Applications of machine learning to machine fault diagnosis: A review and roadmap”. In: *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing* 138 (2020), p. 106587. ISSN: 08883270.

-
- [49] D. D. Lewis. “Naive (Bayes) at forty: The independence assumption in information retrieval”. In: *Machine Learning: ECML-98* (1998), p. 12.
- [50] M. Macchi J. Gómez A.J. Guillén A. Crespo. *On the role of Prognostics and Health Management in advanced maintenance systems*. 2016.
- [51] Oliver Mey et al. *Vibration Measurements on a Rotating Shaft at Different Unbalance Strengths*. 2020.
- [52] R. Keith Mobley. *An introduction to predictive maintenance*. 2. ed. Amsterdam: Butterworth-Heinemann, 2002. ISBN: 0-7506-7531-4.
- [53] John Moubray. *Reliability-centered maintenance*. 2. ed. New York, NY: Industrial Press, 1997. ISBN: 0-8311-3078-4.
- [54] A. Patle and D. S. Chouhan. “SVM kernel functions for classification”. In: *2013 International Conference on Advances in Technology and Engineering (ICATE)*. Piscataway, NJ: IEEE, 2013, pp. 1–9. ISBN: 978-1-4673-5619-0.
- [55] J. P. Pedroso and N. Murata. “Optimisation on support vector machines”. In: *Neural computing: new challenges and perspectives for the new millennium*. Ed. by Shun’ichi Amari. Los Alamitos, Calif.: IEEE Computer Society, 2000, 399–404 vol.6. ISBN: 0-7695-0619-4.
- [56] Wilfried Plaßmann and Detlef Schulz. *Handbuch Elektrotechnik*. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden, 2016. ISBN: 978-3-658-07048-9.
- [57] Prof. Dr. Ing. Joachim Metternich, Tobias Biegel. *Machine Learning Applications Predictive Maintenance Convolutional Neural Networks*.
- [58] Prof. Dr.-Ing. U. Klingauf, Henrik Simon, David Hünemohr. *Machine Learning Applications: PHM in Aviation*.
- [59] Prof. Dr.-Ing. U. Klingauf, Max Weigert, Lorenz Dingeldein. *Machine Learning Applications Prognosis: Forecast Frameworks*. Ed. by Institute of Flight Systems and Automatic Control.
- [60] Prof. Dr.-Ing. Uwe Klingauf. *Machine Learning Applications*. 2022.
- [61] R. B. Randall and J. Antoni. “An introduction to PHM in aerospace applications”. In: *IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine* 32 (2017), pp. 4–11.
- [62] Sebastian Raschka. *Naive Bayes and Text Classification I - Introduction and Theory*. URL: <http://arxiv.org/pdf/1410.5329v4>.
- [63] S. Wold and M. Sjöström. “NN classification problems in chemistry”. In: *Analytica Chimica Acta* 186 (1986), pp. 1–17.
- [64] Sascha Grollmisch, Jakob Abeßer, Judith Liebetrau, Hanna Lukashevich. *IDMT-ISA-ELECTRIC-ENGINE*. 2019. URL: <https://www.idmt.fraunhofer.de/en/publications/datasets/isa-electric-engine.html>.
- [65] Sule Selcuk. “Predictive maintenance, its implementation and latest trends”. In: *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part B: Journal of Engineering Manufacture* 231.9 (2017), pp. 1670–1679. ISSN: 0954-4054.
- [66] Abdel-Nasser Sharkawy. “Principle of Neural Network and Its Main Types: Review”. In: *Journal of Advances in Applied & Computational Mathematics* 7 (2020), pp. 8–19.

-
- [67] Wang Shuo and Yao Xin. "Multiclass Imbalance Problems: Analysis and Potential Solutions". In: *IEEE transactions on systems, man, and cybernetics. Part B, Cybernetics : a publication of the IEEE Systems, Man, and Cybernetics Society* 42.4 (2012), pp. 1119–1130. ISSN: 1083-4419.
- [68] R. K. Sinha et al. "21 - Plant life management (PLiM) practices for pressurised heavy water nuclear reactors (PHWR)". In: *Understanding and mitigating ageing in nuclear power plants*. Ed. by Philip G. Tipping. Woodhead Publishing series in energy. Oxford and Cambridge: Woodhead Publ, 2010, pp. 732–794. ISBN: 978-1-84569-511-8. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9781845695118500214>.
- [69] T. Liu et al. "A survey of PHM for wind turbine systems". In: *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing* 115 (2019), pp. 4–25. ISSN: 08883270.
- [70] Javad Taghipour and Morteza Dardel. "Steady state dynamics and robustness of a harmonically excited essentially nonlinear oscillator coupled with a two-DOF nonlinear energy sink". In: *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing* 62-63 (2015), pp. 164–182. ISSN: 08883270. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0888327015001442>.
- [71] Thomas C. Redman. *The impact of poor data quality on the typical enterprise*. 1998.
- [72] TU Darmstadt FSR, ed. *ETHAN ADP Kickoff slides*. 2022.
- [73] Vinayak Tyagi. *NASA Bearing Dataset*. 16.05.2020. URL: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/vinayak123tyagi/bearing-dataset>.
- [74] *UCI Machine Learning Repository: AI4I 2020 Predictive Maintenance Dataset Data Set*. 12.03.2023. URL: <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/AI4I+2020+Predictive+Maintenance+Dataset>.
- [75] *What are Neural Networks? | IBM*. 2.04.2023. URL: <https://www.ibm.com/topics/neural-networks>.
- [76] *What is Corrective Maintenance? (Definition, Pros, Cons and Examples)*. 30.03.2023. URL: <https://www.twi-global.com/technical-knowledge/faqs/what-is-corrective-maintenance#Examples>.
- [77] *What is Naïve Bayes | IBM*. 2.04.2023. URL: <https://www.ibm.com/topics/naive-bayes>.
- [78] *What is Preventive Maintenance? Types, Examples and Benefits | IBM*. 31.03.2023. URL: <https://www.ibm.com/topics/what-is-preventive-maintenance>.
- [79] Prasetyo Wibowo and Chastine Fatichah. "An in-depth performance analysis of the oversampling techniques for high-class imbalanced dataset". In: *Register: Jurnal Ilmiah Teknologi Sistem Informasi* 7.1 (2021), p. 63. ISSN: 2502-3357.
- [80] Tiago Zonta. *Predictive Useful Life based into telemetry*. 6.08.2020. URL: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/tiagotgoz/predictive-useful-life-based-into-telemetry>.
- [81] Tiago Zonta et al. "Predictive maintenance in the Industry 4.0: A systematic literature review". In: *Computers & Industrial Engineering* 150 (2020), p. 106889. ISSN: 0360-8352. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360835220305787>.

Appendix

A Plots/Figures/Tables Chapter 3

Figure A.1: Concept of Operation

Regression		Classification	
Pros	Cons	Pros	Cons
Predicting continuous output	Easy to be affected by outliers	Familiarity	Cannot predict continuous value
Easy to find trend and pattern of dataset	Overfitting	Suitable to evaluate degrading system	
Easy to interpret		Predict output as a categorical type	

Figure A.2: Feature Comparison

Design Requirements	Description	Functional Requirements
DR 1	Suitable data set	FR1, FR2, FR3, FR4, FR5
DR 2	Anomaly detection	FR5 ,FR6, FR7
DR 3	Data manipulation	FR3, FR4, FR6
DR 4	Evaluation of influences on diagnostic performance	FR4, FR6, FR7, FR8

Figure A.3: Design Requirements

Functional Requirements	Description	Design Requirements
FR 1	Input data shall be an electrical signal with ~20kHz sampling frequency	DR 1
FR 2	Input data shall contain more than 4 variables	DR 1
FR 3	Input data shall contain error and non-gaussian noise	DR 1
FR 4	Input data shall be 5-10 million data points for ML and to manipulate	DR 1, DR 3, DR 4
FR 5	Use sensors to detect anomaly in the electrical system	DR 1, DR 2
FR 6	Impact on quality shall be diagnosed	DR 2, DR 3, DR 4
FR 7	Output for ML shall be categorical	DR 2, DR 3, DR 4
FR 8	Continuously corrupted data set until accuracy dropped to 70%	DR4

Figure A.4: Functional Requirements

Critical Project Element	Description	Functional Requirements
[E1] Data Characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Electrical signal with high sampling frequency around 20kHz - Contains 4+ variables - Noticeable error and non-gaussian noise in the original data set - Large size of data set for ML 	<p style="text-align: center;">FR1</p> <p style="text-align: center;">FR2</p> <p style="text-align: center;">FR3</p> <p style="text-align: center;">FR4</p>
[E2] Input Corruption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - System error - Operational error - Impact on data quality 	<p style="text-align: center;">FR5</p> <p style="text-align: center;">FR5</p> <p style="text-align: center;">FR6</p>
[E3] Features	-Classification (Categorical output. i.e. Healthy or Faulty)	FR7
[E4] ML Models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fine Tree - Naive Bayes - NNN 	FR4
[E5] Data Quality Evaluation	-Accuracy 70% + compared to original data assessment	FR8

Figure A.5: Critical Project Elements

Subteam leads	Data Engineer	ML Engineer	QC Engineer
Project Element	Data Understanding	Data Preparation/ Modeling	Evaluation
Level 1	<p>Create a Dataset that contains multiple runs</p> <p>Relationship between variable understanding</p>	<p>Implement 1 ML model and use it to predict new data</p> <p>Manual labeling</p> <p>Reduction to feasible sensors</p> <p>Set 2 bins between the lowest accepted accuracy and maximum accuracy</p>	<p>Consider 1 type of data corruption and size reduction</p> <p>Evaluate precision and recall</p>
Level 2	<p>Data Contains added noise and random spikes</p> <p>Every run has a randomized path</p> <p>All feedback weights are randomized</p> <p>Randomization is completed using non-Gaussian distribution</p>	<p>Implement 2 ML models and use them to predict new data</p> <p>Manual labeling</p> <p>Reduction to feasible sensors</p> <p>Set 4 bins between the lowest accepted accuracy and maximum accuracy</p>	<p>Consider multiple types of data corruption and size reduction separately</p> <p>Evaluate precision, recall and F1 score</p>
Level 3	<p>Sensors also have noise</p>	<p>Implement 3 ML models and use them to predict new data</p> <p>Manual labeling</p> <p>Reduction to feasible sensors</p> <p>Set 6 bins between the lowest accepted accuracy and maximum accuracy</p>	<p>Consider multiple types of data corruption and size reduction all together</p> <p>Evaluate precision, recall, F1 score and AUC</p>

Figure A.6: Level of Success

Figure A.7: Verification and Validation

Figure A.8: Work Breakdown Structure diagram

B Plots/Figures/Tables Chapter 4

Figure B.1: Positive Wave Shape (RR)

Figure B.2: Negative Wave Shape (RR)

Figure B.3: Positive Wave Cases (RR)

Figure B.4: Negative Wave Cases (RR)

Figure B.5: Positive Waves Mean And Median (RR)

Figure B.6: Negative Waves Mean And Median (RR)

Figure B.7: Shifting k, Fixed S (RR)

Figure B.8: Shifting S, Fixed k (RR)

Figure B.9: Positioning of Both Positive and Negative Waves Across 2000 Runs

Figure B.10: Positioning of Positive Waves Across 2000 Runs

Figure B.11: Positioning of Negative Waves Across 2000 Runs

Figure B.12: Overview of the Circuit

Figure B.13: Input into Simulink

Figure B.14: Flight Input Block

Figure B.15: Electrical Circuit

Figure B.16: DC Block

Figure B.17: DC System Scopes Block

Figure B.18: AC Block

Figure B.19: AC System Scopes Block

Figure B.20: Physical Sensors

Figure B.21: Mechanical Sensors Block

Figure B.22: Rotation Scope Block

Figure B.23: Torque Scope Block

Figure B.24: Temperature Scope Block

Figure B.25: Feedback System Overview

Figure B.26: Feedback System Block

Figure B.27: Temperature Effect Block

Figure B.28: Torque Effect Block

Figure B.29: Angle Effect Block

Figure B.30: Velocity Effect Block

Figure B.31: Internal Break Detection Block

Variable Sensors Correlation

DC Current	6.806e-05	1	-0.04437	0.2539	0.9635	-0.7309	0.3318	0.3247	-0.6817	-0.6817	-0.6817	-0.7112	0.3769	0.7876	-0.3826
AC Current	-8.304e-05	0.9635	-0.04784	0.2933	1	-0.7381	0.2288	0.3538	-0.6925	-0.6924	-0.6924	-0.6992	0.3208	0.7284	-0.3697
Angular Momentum	-6.282e-05	0.7876	-0.03471	0.2465	0.7284	-0.5632	0.7997	0.2627	-0.5127	-0.5127	-0.5127	-0.6279	0.6772	1	-0.35
Motor Angular Velocity	-0.0001067	0.3318	-0.02037	0.09113	0.2288	-0.1362	1	0.2137	-0.1046	-0.1045	-0.1046	-0.3016	0.753	0.7997	-0.1739
Power	-0.0006837	0.3769	-0.0291	0.09789	0.3208	-0.176	0.753	0.7079	-0.1511	-0.1511	-0.1511	-0.2953	1	0.6772	-0.1652
AC Voltage	-0.0004557	0.2539	-0.01111	1	0.2933	-0.266	0.09113	0.07354	-0.2504	-0.2504	-0.2504	-0.2536	0.09789	0.2465	-0.1288
Torque	-0.0007177	0.3247	-0.02992	0.07354	0.3538	-0.1692	0.2137	1	-0.1634	-0.1634	-0.1634	-0.2369	0.7079	0.2627	-0.09508
DC Voltage	1	6.806e-05	6.552e-05	-0.0004557	-8.304e-05	-0.0004447	-0.0001067	-0.0007177	-0.000465	-0.0004653	-0.0004653	-0.0002896	-0.0006837	-6.282e-05	-0.0001456
DC Resistance	6.552e-05	-0.04437	1	-0.01111	-0.04784	0.01526	-0.02037	-0.02992	0.01316	0.01316	0.01316	0.01747	-0.0291	-0.03471	0.01024
Temp Stator B	-0.0004653	-0.6817	0.01316	-0.2504	-0.6924	0.9914	-0.1045	-0.1634	1	1	1	0.8022	-0.1511	-0.5127	0.31
Temp Stator A	-0.000465	-0.6817	0.01316	-0.2504	-0.6925	0.9915	-0.1046	-0.1634	1	1	1	0.8022	-0.1511	-0.5127	0.31
Temp Stator C	-0.0004653	-0.6817	0.01316	-0.2504	-0.6924	0.9914	-0.1046	-0.1634	1	1	1	0.8022	-0.1511	-0.5127	0.31
Motor Angle	-0.0004447	-0.7309	0.01526	-0.266	-0.7381	1	-0.1362	-0.1692	0.9915	0.9914	0.9914	0.8357	-0.176	-0.5632	0.3286
Temp Rotor	-0.0002896	-0.7112	0.01747	-0.2536	-0.6992	0.8357	-0.3016	-0.2369	0.8022	0.8022	0.8022	1	-0.2953	-0.6279	0.3572
TruthOP	-0.0001456	-0.3826	0.01024	-0.1288	-0.3697	0.3286	-0.1739	-0.09508	0.31	0.31	0.31	0.3572	-0.1652	-0.35	1

Figure B.32: Truth Output Correlation Matrix

Figure B.33: Result of ML Trained Models

Figure B.34: Resulting Correlation Matrix from the Manual Labelling Method

Figure B.35: Data Distribution of 20% Corrupted Output

Figure B.36: Confusion Matrix of Validation set for 20% Corrupted Output

Figure B.37: Confusion Matrix of Test set for 20% Corrupted Output

Figure B.38: AUC of Validation set for 20% Corrupted Output

Figure B.39: AUC of Test set for 20% Corrupted Output

Figure B.40: 5% Corrupted Output Correlation Matrix

Figure B.41: Confusion Matrix for the FT at 200 and 400 samples per row delay, using the method M1V1

C Plots/Figures/Tables Chapter 5

C.1 Reduce F_s with Uncorrupted data

Figure C.1: 4 Metrics of Fine Tree with Down Sampling by the factor of 1-10 in M1

Figure C.2: 4 Metrics of Naive Bayes with Down Sampling by the factor of 1-10 in M1

Figure C.3: AUC of Naive Bayes with Down Sampling by the factor of 1-10 in M1

Figure C.4: 4 Metrics of Narrow Neural Network with Down Sampling by the factor of 1-10 in M1

Figure C.5: AUC of Narrow Neural Network with Down Sampling by the factor of 1-10 in M1

C.2 Transmission Delay M1 with Uncorrupted data

Figure C.6: 4 Metrics of Fine Tree with 0-20s Transmission Delay

Figure C.7: AUC of Naive Bayes with 0-20s Transmission Delay

Figure C.8: AUC of Naive Bayes with 0-20s Transmission Delay

Figure C.9: 4 Metrics of Narrow Neural Network with 0-20s Transmission Delay

Figure C.10: AUC of Narrow Neural Network with 0-20s Transmission Delay

C.3 Transmission Delay M1 Combination Cases with Uncorrupted data

Figure C.11: 4 Metrics of Fine Tree with Combination of Transmission Delay and Down Sampling in M1

Figure C.12: 4 Metrics of Naive Bayes with Combination of Transmission Delay and Down Sampling in M1

Figure C.13: AUC of Naive Bayes with Combination of Transmission Delay and Down Sampling in M1

Figure C.14: 4 Metrics of Narrow Neural Network with Combination of Transmission Delay and Down Sampling in M1

Figure C.15: AUC of Narrow Neural Network with Combination of Transmission Delay and Down Sampling in M1

C.4 M1 trained with corrupted data

Figure C.16: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Fine Tree Model with 20s Transmission Delay

Figure C.17: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Fine Tree Model with Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.18: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Fine Tree Model with 20s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.19: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Fine Tree Model with 80s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.20: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Naive Bayes Model with 20s Transmission Delay

Figure C.21: AUC of Corrupted Naive Bayes Model with 20s Transmission Delay

Figure C.22: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Naive Bayes Model with Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.23: AUC of Corrupted Naive Bayes Model with Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.24: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Naive Bayes Model with 20s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.25: AUC of Corrupted Naive Bayes Model with 20s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.26: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Naive Bayes Model with 80s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.27: AUC of Corrupted Naive Bayes Model with 80s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.28: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Narrow Neural Network Model with 20s Transmission Delay

Figure C.29: AUC of Corrupted Narrow Neural Network Model with 20s Transmission Delay

Figure C.30: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Narrow Neural Network Model with Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.31: AUC of Corrupted Narrow Neural Network Model with Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.32: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Narrow Neural Network Model with 20s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.33: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Narrow Neural Network Model with 20s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.34: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Narrow Neural Network Model with 80s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.35: AUC of Corrupted Narrow Neural Network Model with 80s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10

C.5 Transmission Delay M2 Case 1

Figure C.36: AUC of Fine Tree Model with a Maximum M2 Transmission Delay of 400s

Figure C.37: AUC curve of Naive Bayes with a Maximum M2 Transmission Delay of 20s

Figure C.38: AUC curve of Narrow Neural Network with a Maximum M2 Transmission Delay of 20s

C.6 Transmission Delay M2 Case 2

Figure C.39: AUC curve of Naive Bays with a maximum Transmission Delay of 20s and a varying percentage made with M2

Figure C.40: AUC curve of Narrow Neural Network with a maximum Transmission Delay of 20s and a varying percentage made with M2

C.7 M2 Case 2 Combination Case

Figure C.41: AUC curve of Naive Bayes with a maximum Transmission Delay of 20s made with M2 and downsampling

Figure C.42: AUC curve of Narrow Neural Network with a maximum Transmission Delay of 20s made with M2 and downsampling

C.8 M2 Case 1 trained with corrupted data

Figure C.43: AUC curve corrupted of Narrow Neural Network with a maximum Transmission Delay of 20s made with M2 trained on downsampling factor of 10

Figure C.44: AUC curve corrupted of Narrow Neural Network with a maximum Transmission Delay of 20s made with M2 trained on downsampling factor of 10 and time delay of 80s

Figure C.45: AUC curve corrupted of Narrow Neural Network with a maximum Transmission Delay of 20s made with M2 trained on downsampling factor of 10

Figure C.46: AUC curve corrupted of Narrow Neural Network Model with a maximum Transmission Delay of 20s made with M2

Figure C.47: AUC curve corrupted of Naive Bays with a maximum Transmission Delay of 20s made with M2 trained on downsampling factor of 10

Figure C.48: AUC curve corrupted of Naive Bays with a maximum Transmission Delay of 20s made with M2 trained on time delay of 80s

Figure C.49: AUC curve corrupted of Naive Bays with a maximum Transmission Delay of 20s made with M2 trained on downsampling factor of 10 and time delay of 80s

Figure C.50: AUC curve corrupted of Naive Bays with a maximum Transmission Delay of 20s made with M2

C.9 M3 Transmission Delay with uncorrupted data

Figure C.51: 4 Metrics of Fine Tree with 0-20s Transmission Delay

Figure C.52: AUC of Fine Tree with 0-20s Transmission Delay

Figure C.53: 4 Metrics of Naive Bayes with 0-20s Transmission Delay

Figure C.54: AUC of Naive Bayes with 0-20s Transmission Delay

Figure C.55: 4 Metrics of Narrow Neural Network with 0-20s Transmission Delay

Figure C.56: AUC of Narrow Neural Network with 0-20s Transmission Delay

C.10 M3 combination cases trained with corrupted data

Figure C.57: 4 Metrics of Fine Tree with Combination of Transmission Delay and Down Sampling

Figure C.58: 4 Metrics of Naive Bayes with Combination of Transmission Delay and Down Sampling

Figure C.59: AUC of Naive Bayes with Combination of Transmission Delay and Down Sampling

Figure C.60: 4 Metrics of NNN with Combination of Transmission Delay and Down Sampling

Figure C.61: AUC of Narrow Neural Network with Combination of Transmission Delay and Down Sampling

C.11 M3 trained with corrupted data

Figure C.62: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Fine Tree Model with 20s Transmission Delay

Figure C.63: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Fine Tree Model with Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.64: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Fine Tree Model with 20s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.65: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Fine Tree Model with 80s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.66: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Naive Bayes Model with 20s Transmission Delay

Figure C.67: AUC of Corrupted Naive Bayes Model with 20s Transmission Delay

Figure C.68: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Naive Bayes Model with Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.69: AUC of Corrupted Naive Bayes Model with Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.70: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Naive Bayes Model with 20s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.71: AUC of Corrupted Naive Bayes Model with 20s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.72: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Naive Bayes Model with 80s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.73: AUC of Corrupted Naive Bayes Model with 80s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.74: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Narrow Neural Network Model with 20s Transmission Delay

Figure C.75: AUC of Corrupted Narrow Neural Network Model with 20s Transmission Delay

Figure C.76: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Narrow Neural Network Model with Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.77: AUC of Corrupted Narrow Neural Network Model with Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.78: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Narrow Neural Network Model with 20s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.79: AUC of Corrupted Narrow Neural Network Model with 20s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.80: 4 Metrics of Corrupted Narrow Neural Network Model with 80s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10

Figure C.81: AUC of Corrupted Narrow Neural Network Model with 80s Transmission Delay and Size Reduction by 10